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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

BIRTH OF A SIBYL: THE MEDIEVAL CONNECTION¹

PART 1

1. A fateful question and a new investigation

In our journey across the original sources of the legends of the Apennine Sibyl and the Lakes of Pilatus, a journey which we have been carrying out for many years and is currently resulting in a number of feature articles providing an unprecedented insight into the fascinating mythical world of the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy, the time has come to confront with a most critical question.

¹ Released on December 12th, 21st, 24th, 26th, 28th, 30th December 2018 and 2nd, 3rd, 6th, 7th, 10th, 12th and 13th January 2019 (http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_SibylsCore.asp)

A fundamental, fateful question - one that many lovers of this legendary lore will not like at all, and yet a question we are required to ask ourselves if we want to keep our firm adherence and unswerving commitment to the principles of scientific investigation, rooted in the unbiased scrutiny of all available sources and pieces of evidence.

The question is articulated as follows: has a Sibyl ever resided beneath the sinister peak of Mount Sibyl?

Fig. 1 - The crests leading to the peak of Mount Sibyl, a mountain which raises in the Italian Apennines

This might look like a silly, wacky question. Of course, we are not wondering whether a magical sort of fairy kingdom has ever been established, in actual reality, under the ridges of Mount Sibyl (Fig. 1), a mountain which does exist in our physical world and raises in a remote region of central Italy: sure enough, nothing the like has ever existed, with gorgeous palaces hidden beneath the rocky fastnesses, and luscious gardens and opulent treasures and beautiful damsels awaiting unblemished knights and daring visitors, a subterranean realm whose nasty queen craved to snatch their soul away and convict them to an eternal imprisonment in her own lustful arms, the evil arms of an Apennine Sibyl. That's the legend.

The question we pose is quite different: did the tradition concerning an Apennine Sibyl living beneath Mount Sibyl actually emerge, as a fully

original, native tale, from the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range? Was this lore truly generated in the region of Mount Sibyl, or was it adapted and transplanted there from some different cultural areas and geographic territories into that specific, particular spot of land?

Was the Apennine Sibyl's legend born there, or has it come from somewhere else?

As we presented in our previous series of articles *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, the legend of the Sibyl of the Apennines appears to have come out at the beginning of the fifteenth century, as a shining, lonely star, from a sort of echoing void, an impenetrable mist, starting from there her successful travel into the subsequent ages (Fig. 2). We concluded those articles by asking ourselves a question: has that Sibyl really journeyed a long way across the centuries and through that inscrutable fog, after having started her travel in ancient times and having remained unseen until she emerged in the fifteenth century? Or, was she the more recent product of some strange condensation of that thick, whirling mist, in which her myth took form not in antiquity, but just very close to the beginning of the fifteenth century?

Did the Sibyl arise from the condensation of any sort of peculiar nature of that place, the Sibillini Mountain Range, having been subsequently clad with additional mythical themes taken from other tales and stories?

We feel that we are now ready to address this essential issue, by putting together a large number of clues we have collected in the course of our multi-year search on the topic: the Apennine Sibyl as a target of an unprecedented investigation, which may contribute to make a significant number of steps ahead in the direction of a new understanding of the sibilline mystery and tradition, closely linked to the mysterious lore concerning the Lakes of Pilatus, which lies just a few miles away.

So what are we going to do now?

We will fathom that impenetrable mist, venturing ourselves into the unexplored void which lies before the fifteenth century.

Fig. 2 - The image we presented in the final paragraph of our previous article “The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle”, with the Sibyl emerging from the mists of time at the beginning of the fifteenth century (composite image by the author)

We will do what has never been done before: we will highlight the Apennine Sibyl's hidden connections to other traditions and legendary tales, originated in different regions and from different literary works. We will show that a large portion of the sibilline narration actually comes from other, different lore. And, finally, we will analyse the very nature of the site where the Sibyl's cave lies, so as to find the specific link that will push our research much further in the understanding of this obscure legend.

Our goal is to uncover the real essence of the myth of the Apennine Sibyl, the inner core of her ancient legend. We will remove all literary additions conferred to her legendary tale across the centuries. We will take off all the concentric layers that encircle and suffocate her true mythical nucleus, the

way a rose is deprived of the outer petals which shelter the fragrant redolence of its central heart. We will clean her figure by wiping out the narrative elements that have been added with time to her story, borrowed from several different mythical tales. We will strip all her disguises off so as to be able to see her true, antique semblance.

We will do this by taking advantage of our previous articles, including *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, *Antoine de la Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*, *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl - The literary truth about the magical doors set beneath Mount Sibyl*, *The knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and his forefathers: Huon d'Auvergne*, *The knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and his forefathers: Huon of Bordeaux*, *World of the Sibyl: the Italian Apennines and the Sibillini Mountain Range*, and others. We will add to that a large number of new findings which will cast a new light on the whole matter.

Let's start and see what kind of inscrutable lands we are about to attain.

2. *The Sibyl that wasn't there in antiquity*

In our previous series of articles *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, we have definitely reached a conclusion which we consider as remarkably significant: at all appearances, the Apennine Sibyl was not a known oracle, either in the Middle Ages or in antiquity. There is no trace of her, and of her oracular site in the Sibillini Mountain Range, before the beginning of the fifteenth century.

In those articles, we started our search by summarising the literary evidences that, from the fifteenth century onwards, had fostered the idea of a Sibyl who was living beneath a specific mountain situated in central Italy, Mount Sibyl: those evidences included *Guerrino the Wretch*, a chivalric romance written by Andrea da Barberino around 1410, a most successful best-seller for many centuries to come; and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, an account of a visit that a French gentleman, Antoine de la Sale, made to the Sibyl's cliff and cave in 1420.

And there they are, both of them, as you have never seen them before.

In the figure below is *Guerrino the Wretch*, with the romance's initial page and an excerpt on the Sibyl, both taken from manuscript MA297, preserved at the Municipal Library “Angelo Mai” in Bergamo (Italy) and dating to 1468.

Fig. 3 - The opening of Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* and a passage on the Sibyl as they appear in manuscript no. MA297 (Bergamo, Biblioteca Civica “Angelo Mai”) dating to 1468

And then, here is *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, with the opening of Antoine de la Sale's account on the Sibyl as it appears in the astounding illuminated manuscript no. 0653 (0924) preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé) in Chantilly (France).

Fig. 4 - The initial pages of Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, with a passage on the Sibyl, taken from manuscript no. 0653 (0924) preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé) in Chantilly (France), dating to around 1440

Both literary works depicted a cave and a Sibyl, a subterranean kingdom and oracular powers, handsome damsels and fairy illusions which lured visitors into lustful sins, so as to steal their souls and prevent them from enjoying the Salvation brought by Jesus Christ into our world.

However, when we tried to spot any other references to this specific sibilline tale and site in earlier literary sources, we just failed.

No mention of an Apennine Sibyl is found in any known source produced in the centuries of Late and Early Middle Ages. We don't even find a single reference to that Sibyl in the ancient documents contained in the local historical archive of Norcia, which should reasonably contain a number of

quotes referring to such an illustrious inhabitant of the neighbouring mountains.

But nothing is present in the *Charters of the Municipality and People of the Land of Norcia (Statuti del Comune et Populo della Terra di Norcia)*, whose original version dates to year 1346. And nothing is present, either, in a well-informed historical work written in 1869 by Feliciano Patrizi-Forti, a local scholar, in which a bounty of information on ancient Norcia is detailed, yet no reference to a Sibyl of the Apennines is reported - apart from a footnote which is drawn, as we fully explained in our articles, from a 1617 revised edition of Claudius Ptolemy's *Geography*, and not from the original work by Ptolemy himself.

When we pushed ourselves as far back as the age of the Roman Empire, we found out that no reference to that Sibyl is retrievable in Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' enumeration of ten Sibyls contained in his fourth-century *De divinis institutionibus adversus gentes*. The only Italian Sibyls attested by Emperor Constantine's advisor were the Cumaean, the Tiburtine and the Cimmerian, the latter a close relative of the former. As to the Tiburtine, she is easily identified as a good candidate for a Sibyl having her abode in the Italian Apennines: unfortunately, the Apennines that are mentioned in a variety of manuscripts in connection to the Tiburtine Sibyl are the actual ridges where her oracular shrine stood, namely Tibur, or modern Tivoli, not far from Rome, and a long way from the Sibillini Mountain Range.

A number of other references to the existence of an oracular site in the Apennine area, namely a passage taken from the *Historia Augusta* concerning Emperor Claudius II Gothicus, and the excerpt found in Suetonius' *The Twelve Caesars* in relation to Emperor Vitellius, make reference to no Sibyls and provide no clues as to where to locate such site or sites, across the full length of the Apennine chain (some 750 miles long).

We then made a daring attempt at getting first-hand information from the Tabula Peutingeriana, the astounding manuscripted map that depicts the full extension of the Roman Empire as it was around the third century, and even earlier: yet the portion of the chart which portrays the present Sibillini Mountain Range shows no indication of any sibilline site, even though the

Tabula is mainly a road map and might as well omit to signal the presence of places of such nature.

We may also note that, in antiquity, the name of the Sibillini Mountain Range bore no reference to any Sibyls: their precipitous ridges and cliffs were known as Mount Tetricus («Tetricae horrentis rupes» in Publius Vergilius Maro, the «Tetricus mons in Sabinis asperrimus» according to Servius Marius Honoratus), with reference to the stern, gloomy mood of the inhabitants of the place, as we detailed in our previous article *World of the Sibyl: the Italian Apennines and the Sibillini Mountain Range*.

So, the current state-of-the-art in the search for our elusive Apennine Sibyl can be presented as follows: we have detected a suspicious lack of early mentions of that sibilline oracle in both medieval and Roman literary traditions. An absence which is confirmed by the many essays published throughout more than a century by all the scholars who have made efforts to unveil the true lineage of the Apennine Sibyl: absolutely naught.

And this is definitely no news. We have just reached the very same conclusion that Leandro Alberti, an illustrious Dominican friar, a geographer and a historian, had already stated in the year 1550, centuries ahead of us. In his *Descrittione di tutta l'Italia (A General Description of Italy)*, this clever, caustic author set down all his disbelief as to the hidden inhabitant of the Sibillini Mountain Range:

«It comes as a bit of a surprise that so many years have elapsed, from the time when this Cavern was discovered and saluted as the Sibyl's abode, and no mention of it has ever been recorded at all, neither in the works by Strabo nor in Pliny's nor in the writings of any other inquisitive Author, in search of oddities and rarities. And yet every reader can consider by himself how scrupulously Strabo has provided a full description of the Caves and hollows that are to be found in Cuma, and Baiæ, and Naples; and Pliny, as well, has written most accurate reports of the many wonders of Nature; however, no one of them ever wrote a single word about that Cavern, nor provided any accounts as regards the cave's folk tale».

[In the original Italian text: «In vero ella è cosa molto maravigliosa, che siano passati tanti anni, ne li quali si dice esser stata ritrovata questa Caverna, & esser quivi la Sibilla, & che mai non sia stato fatto alcuna

memoria d'essa da Strabone, ne da Plinio, ne da altro curioso scrittore, & vestigatore delle cose rare. Vedemo pur esser stato molto diligente Strabone in descrivere le Grotti, & spelunche, che sono a Cuma, a Baia, & a Napoli, & parimente Plinio rammentando i miracoli della Natura, & mai pur una minima parola hanno scritto di quella Grotta, ò vero della favola volgare di essa»].

Fig. 5 - The passage on the Apennine Sibyl taken from Leandro Alberti's *Descrittione di tutta Italia*, printed in 1550 in Bologna

Today, just as in 1550, we regard as a clue of the utmost significance the fact that no reference about an Apennine Sibyl is to be found before the beginning of the fifteenth century. And we fully agree with Leandro Alberti when he states the following:

«[...] if the cave and lake had been really known in antiquity, there is no doubt that its finding would have been duly recorded, as actually was the case for the Oracle at Delphi, and Podalirius, and Avernus, and the Hollow and Cave of the said Cumæan Sibyl, and many other places likewise, as well as caverns, Lakes, Trees, Rivers, Springs, Woods, Temples, Altars and further Oracles of the same kind, where evil Spirits are said to utter deceitful words to beguile men».

[In the original Italian text: «se [la caverna e il lago] fossero stati osservati dagli antichi, non dubito che ne sarebbe stato fatto memoria, sicome e fatto dell'Oracolo di Delpho, di Podalirio, dell'Averno, & dell'Antro, & Spelunca della detta Sibilla Cuma, & parimente de molti altri luoghi, sicome di spelunche, Laghi, Alberi, Fiumi, Fontane, Selve, Tempii, Sacelli, & simili altri Oracoli, ove davano risposta i bugiardi Demonii per ingannare gli huomini»].

So, it is a fact that no reference to a Sibyl of the Apennines can be detected if we push ourselves back across the ages and before the fifteenth century. We are stuck, just like all modern researchers before us and Leandro Alberti either, to the earliest, much-known mentions we are well accustomed to: Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino The Wretch* and Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

Is that the end of the story? No.

Because all other scholars just stopped here. Or, they just tried to make fanciful assumptions about some sort of antique, mythical lineage to which the Appennine Sibyl might possibly be referred: for instance, a classical Sibyl, or the ancient goddess Cybele.

Instead, we are moving further.

We are starting to sniff the scent of a trail, the fragrance of a trace we had already begun to follow in our previous articles *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and His Forefathers*, *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl - The Literary Truth about the Magical Doors Set beneath Mount Sibyl* and *Antoine de la Sale and the Magical Bridge Concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*: a faint whiff of known literary traditions which quietly, secretly seem to leak out from the Apennine Sibyl's legend and lore.

A whiff that no one seems to have ever noticed before.

As Leandro Alberti wrote, «I am convinced that not much time has passed since the rumour about that Cavern and lake has spread» («Credo non esser molto tempo che siano state volgate queste favole di detta Caverna, e del detto lago» in the original Italian text). Again, we fully agree.

The Apennine Sibyl is not so old as she would like us to believe. Most probably, the sibilline tale is much younger than we think, possibly not much older than the fifteenth century itself. And this tale contains many elements which are drawn from other legendary narrations: additions, and extensions, suitably superimposed to an original, central mythical core.

Let's start following this trail. Let's unmask the additions and uncover the extensions. By performing this operation, we will move closer and closer to the true core of the legend. The inner nucleus, the essential heart, of the Apennine Sibyl's mythical tale.

3. Dismantling Antoine de la Sale's magical bridge

In the preceding chapter, we highlighted the lack of any reference to the existence of an Apennine Sibyl in the centuries spanning before the fifteenth: a thoroughly suspicious piece of evidence which seems to signify that a different story is to be told about that Sibyl of the Apennines.

If no such Sibyl is mentioned in both medieval and Roman literary traditions, is that mythical narrative much younger than we used to consider? Did the Sibyl take possession of her abode amid the Sibillini Mountain Range not much before the beginning of the fifteenth century?

Because, as we already stated, there is some sort of strange whiff we sense, an odd feeling we have that something, with that Sibyl, might be somehow wrong.

And the wrong elements appear to pour in when we start to consider a number of literary facts, which pop up one after another as we consider, with increased, careful attention, the two fundamental cornerstones of the Apennine Sibyl's legendary lore: Andrea da Barberino's "Guerrino The Wretch" and Antoine de la Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl".

When we take in our hands the two fifteenth-century works, which boosted the fame of the formerly-unknown, previously-unnoticed Sibyl across the

nations of Europe and across many centuries to come, we begin to notice some flaws, a number of odd inconsistencies.

Let's open the pages of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) preserved at the Musée Condé, in the library of the Castle of Chantilly, north of Paris. This is one of the two existing instances of Antoine de la Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl", dating around year 1440, and containing fine miniatures of the visit that the French gentleman paid to the Sibyl's cave in 1420.

Fig. 6 - Mount Sibyl and the Sibyl's cave as they appear in a miniature contained in the original work by Antoine de la Sale (folium 6 of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château - Musée Condé in Chantilly)

At folium 11v we find a first suspicious piece of narrative that Antoine de la Sale wrote down in his travel account. When he reports the tales told to him by the local peasants about what was to be encountered in the inner recesses of the Apennine Sibyl's cave, the French gentleman mentions a bridge, a very magical instance of a bridge:

«Then you find a bridge, made of some unknown material, but it is said to be less than a single foot wide and it seems to be extending far ahead. Below the bridge, a ghastly, precipitating abyss [...] Yet as soon as you put both feet on the bridge, it becomes large enough; and the more you step ahead, the more it widens and the abyss becomes shallower» [in the original French text: «Lors trouve len un pont, que len ne scet de quoy il est mais est advis quil nait mie un pie de large et samble estre moult long.

Dessousz ce pont a tres grant et hydeux abisme de parfondeur [...] Mais aussi tost quon a les deux piez sur ce pont il est assez large; et tant vait on plus avant tant est plus est large et moins creux»].

Fig. 7 - The excerpt on the magically narrow bridge taken from folia 11v and 12r of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*

Very nice, very interesting, very thrilling: what a sinister magical place this Italian cavern must be, and how intriguing this account by de la Sale sounds to his listener's ears.

Too bad this very special bridge is taken straight out from a different literary tradition, and bravely copied by Antoine de la Sale into his work on the Apennine Sibyl.

As we fully explained in our previous article “Antoine de la Sale and the Magical Bridge Concealed beneath Mount Sibyl”, the magical bridge, narrow as a razor's edge but widening itself when trodden by a true, sincere believer, is part of a most renowned literary tradition spanning through Europe across a thousand years, and throughout the Middle Ages.

Where did Antoine de la Sale take this bridge from? There are two main channels through which he received and became fully acquainted with the ancient tradition of the narrow bridge.

The first channel is chivalry and chivalric romances.

Antoine de la Sale was a refined courtier and a man of letters, so he was perfectly aware of the chivalric literature of his own time. When in 1455 he wrote *The History and Pleasant Chronicle of Little Jehan de Saintré and the Young Lady of the Fair Cousins* (*L'Hystoire et plaisante cronicque du Petit Jehan de Saintré et de la jeune Dame des Belles Cousines*), he built a literary account of the education of a perfect, ideal young knight, a most influential and most-read book for hundreds of years. And he included, in Chapter III, words that show his full knowledge of the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian legend: «[...] the valorous achievements, the imperishable memories, and the ever-glorious feats of a Launcelot, a Gauvain, a Tristan, of Giron, the courteous, and of the other heroes of the Round Table» [in the original French text: «[...] les grans vaillances, les grans emprises et les chevalereux fais de Lancelot, de Gauvain, de Tristan, de Giron le Courtois et des autres preux de la Table Ronde»]. In addition to that, Antoine de la Sale was born in the French region of Provence, so he was certainly fully acquainted with the *Chansons de Geste*, the French medieval epic poems.

And what do we find in such chivalric literature he well knew? Let's take *Huon d'Auvergne*, a chivalric poem belonging to an ancient French-Italian tradition, of which four manuscripts survive (Berlin, Turin, Padua, Bologna) dating between 1341 and 1441. In manuscript n. 32 preserved at the Biblioteca del Seminario Vescovile in Padova, whose original literary source is dated by scholars to the first half of the fifteenth century, we stumble upon the very same bridge:

«I will tell you how cruel was that bridge: - Its top side is as sharp as an arrow - And it cleaves more easily than a sword [...] first he signed himself with the cross - then they ventured across the bridge with small steps - so that they safely reached the far edge»

[in the original French-Italian text at Folium 101 recto in the Padua manuscript: «La crudelitate del ponte ve voio contere: - Desovra è agudo como quarel d'açere - E pluy ca spada ello taia volentiere [...] primamente

se fè la croxe al vis, - Po se meteno su per lo ponte a pas petis - Tanto che sono oltro el pont sulla ris»].

So that bridge, as narrow as a razor, but turning into a crossable one if the brave believer's faith is strong, is a literary motif we also find in chivalric romances.

And there is even a second source from which Antoine de la Sale may have drawn inspiration for his Sibyl's bridge: the Irish legend of St. Patrick, which refers to a cavern providing an entryway to Purgatory, and which de la Sale well knew, as attested by his work "La Salade", containing a direct reference to the legend of «Saint Patrisse» in «Yrlande», where «a cave is found in which people say that the punishment in Purgatory and the torments in Hell can be seen» [in the original French text: «la est la cave ou se dit que on va veoir les peines de purgatoire et les tourmens d'enfer»].

It is in the ancient manuscripts of the "Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii", dating to the twelfth century, that we find, again, the very same bridge:

«A bridge crossed the river, which was covered with roaring, fiendish flames, which showed three impossible features, to the utter terror of those who had to get through: the first was that it was slippery, so that even if it had been wide enough, no one would be able to set its foot firmly onto it; furthermore, it was so narrow and frail that nobody would dare to stand nor tread on it; third, it was so tall over a river down below that utterly frightful was the vision of the abyss [...] However the knight, who trusted in Jesus [...] bravely entered the bridge and began to walk on it, without sensing nothing slippery under his feet [...] and finding the bridge wider and wider; and after a little while so grew the width of the bridge, that ahead of him it was as large as a public street, and eleven wagons travelling at the same time would enjoy enough space [...] He saw that the broadness of the bridge was growing so much that scarcely he could now see the two sides of it».

[In the original Latin text: «Pons vero protendebatur ultra flumen, sulphurei incendii flamma copertum, in quo tria quasi impossibilia et transeuntibus valde formidanda videbantur, unum quod ita lubricus erat, ut etiam si latus fuerit, nullus vel vix aliquis in eo pedem figere posset; alterum quod tam

strictus et gracilis erat, ut nullus in eo stare vel ambulare valeret; tertium quod tam altus erat, et a flumine remotus ut horrendum esset deorsum aspicere [...] Sed miles Christi fidelis [...] pontem audacter ingressus, coepit pedetentium incedere, nihilque lubrici sub pedibus sentiens [...] eo spatiosorem invenit pontem; et ecce post paululum tanta crevit pontis latitudo, ut publicae viae amplitudinem prae se ferret, et undecim carra sibi obvianta posset excipere [...] vidit latitudinem pontis in tantum excrescere, ut vix ex utraque parte ejus fines posset aspicere»].

Fig. 8 - The magical bridge at folium 144v of manuscript Latin 5137 (*Purgatorium Sancti Patricii*) preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits

In the above figure, the same passage, with a slightly different wording, can be retrieved in manuscript Latin 5137, a version of the “*Purgatorium Sancti Patricii*” dating to the thirteenth century and preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France.

And the matter does not end here. We actually discover that that bridge, the same bridge that Antoine de la Sale decided to include in his account on the Apennine Sibyl, is present in a number of medieval monastic texts, often of Irish origin, all describing the journey of a mortal man into the purgatorial otherworld, like the “*Vision of St. Adamnán*” (eleventh-century), the “*Vision of Alberic*” (twelfth century), the “*Vision of Tnugdalu*” (another twelfth century text), the “*Vision of Sunniulf*”, and then the “*Vision of Ezra*”. And its lineage is even older: this literary piece of narration makes its appearance in the literary tradition of the Western world with the “*Dialogues*”, written in the sixth century by Pope St. Gregory I the Great, with its ultimate origin to be retrieved in an antique Zoroastrian tradition, that of the “*Chinvato Peretu*”, the bridge of judgment, as explained in more detail in my previous article “*Antoine de la Sale and the Magical Bridge Concealed beneath Mount Sibyl*”.

Fig. 9 - A miniature from *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal*, a French manuscripted version of the *Vision of Tnugdalus* dating to 1475 and preserved at the Getty Museum

Is there any remaining uncertainty about the fact that the magical bridge mentioned by Antoine de la Sale has nothing to do with the any genuine tradition connected to the Apennine Sibyl? No, no doubt. Because Andrea da Barberino himself, the author of the chivalric romance “Guerrino the Wretch”, unsheaths a final, conclusive argument before our very eyes .

In his most renowned fifteenth-century work providing a fundamental reference to the Apennine Sibyl's legend and lore, he does mention the same magically narrow bridge as Antoine de la Sale did. However, Andrea da Barberino does not make any literary use of it in the chapters dedicated to the Sibyl; instead, and more correctly, he includes it twice in a subsequent portion of his romance, the portion dedicated to the journey made by his hero Guerrino into a place we already know: the Purgatory of St. Patrick in Ireland.

As I fully described in my previous article, here is how Andrea da Barberino mentions our magical bridge as Guerrino proceeds with his visit through the Purgatory (chapter CLXX):

«... and immediately he was standing on a bridge that crossed the marsh from one side to the other over a large river. And it seemed to him that the bridge was so narrow that nobody could have put one foot ahead of the other. He turned to get back but he could not see the bridge beneath his own eyes. And he saw countless jaws of big snakes and dragons, and it was as if they were waiting for him to fall down. Guerrino had never been so scared as in this predicament. And all the way along the bridge he feared he would fall. And actually he was about to fall: but he called on the Holy Name, and by His mercy the bridge swell to a huge width. And he could go through this perilous passage».

[In the original Italian text: «... e subito fu drito sopra uno ponte che trapassava questo lagune da uno lato al altro sopra uno grande fiume. E parevali questo ponte tanto sottile, che uno piede avanti l'altro non li poteva stare. Lui se volse per tornare e non vide el ponte abasso gli ochi. E vide infinite bocche de grandi serpenti, e dragoni, e pareva che aspetassero che lui cadesse. Anchora non havea avuto Guerino magior paura che questa. E tutta via li pareva de cadere. E pure saria caduto: ma chiamò el santo nome, e per la soa misericordia el ponte se li fece largissimo. E passò de là da questo fortunoso passo»].

And a second instance of the same bridge is encountered a few chapters ahead (chapter CLXXXII):

«And he saw a river that was crossed by so thin and narrow a bridge that there was no small animal that would pass through it, because of his tiny width. He crossed himself and entrusted himself to God. He was taken [by the demons] and placed onto the middle of the bridge, where they left him, then they began to scream at him, and flung stones and shafts at him so that he was about to fall. And he turned to go back , and could see no bridge. So he looked at the bottom where the water was, and saw that it was full of hideous worms and snakes. The bridge was so thin that it was not possible to put one foot ahead of the other. He began to call the name of Jesus Christ from Nazareth, and the bridge started to get wider. As he spoke these words

thrice, he began to sing 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', and the bridge became even larger, and he was through».

[In the original Italian text: «E vide uno fiume cui atraverso li era uno ponte tanto sutile e stretto che lo non è si piccolo animale che havesse potuto passare, tanto era stretto. Lui se fece el segno de la santa croce e recomandose a dio. Fu preso [dai demoni] e posto suxo el mezo del ponte et ivi lo lassorono, e poi cominciarono a cridare et a zitarli pietre e pali per modo che el meschino fu per cadere. E lui se volse indietro per tornare indietro, e non vide ponte. Alhora pose mente nel fundo de laqua, e lo vide pieno de vermini bruti e serpenti. El ponte era si stretto che uno pié inanti l'altro non li cadeva. Lui cominciò a chiamare iesu christo nazareno, e lo ponte si cominciò a largare. E dite queste parole tre volte, cominciò a cantare 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', et el ponte se largava, e lui passò»].

Fig. 10 - The two different excerpts where Guerrino encounters the same magical bridge in *Guerrino the Wretch* (from the 1480 edition printed in Venice)

Here are the flaws, the inconsistencies we talked about at the beginning of this article. Here is the whiff, the scent of a trace, the discordant note, which tells us that something is wrong with the known legend concerning an Apennine Sibyl living under Mount Sibyl, in Italy

We begin to fully understand that this Sibyl of the Apennines has been clothed in garments that do not belong to her true story. She has been

arbitrarily endowed with attributes which pertain to different, more antique traditions.

The magically narrow bridge is one such garment and attribute. We will need to strip the Sibyl of this fake dress, which Antoine de la Sale added to her true figure.

And the bridge is not the only spurious article of clothing that the French man of letter put on her semblance.

There is another one as well: the magical doors. Let's take it off in the next chapter.

4. Antoine de la Sale's magical slamming doors unhinged

In our previous article, we have started to spot the flaws that affect the legendary tradition concerning the Apennine Sibyl: the total lack of mentions in medieval and/or Roman literature, the reference to a magical narrow bridge that is taken straight from earlier mythical narratives which have nothing to do with that sibilline oracle. All such clues seem to indicate that an original core making up a legend rooted in the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range has been veiled by later additions, with no relation at all with the inner nucleus of the myth.

Now we are going to confront with another instance of this masking process: a further addition to the deep core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend, providing another shield to the ultimate truth of this fascinating tale.

Let's take again in our hands the pages of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) preserved at the Musée Condé in Chantilly, France. As we know, it is the original version of Antoine de la Sale's fifteenth-century *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*. At folia 11r and then 12r we find a sinister, blood-curdling piece of narration: the famous ever-slamming metal doors, hidden beneath the mysterious peak of Mount Sibyl, in the darkest bowels of the Sibyl's cavern:

«... within that cave, up to the metal doors, which slam ceaselessly day and night, opening wide and then shutting close again [...] in the cavern, there are two doors made of metal, slamming without rest as I reported above. He said that these doors slam so savagely that everyone who wishes to enter is made aware that nobody can get in without being caught between them and wholly crushed. And that was what frightened the two Germans the more...».

[In the original French text: «... dedans ceste cave, jusques es portes de metal, qui jour et nuyt sans cesser batent, clouant et ouvrant [...] à l'endroit de la cave, sont les deux portes de metal, qui batent sans cesser ainsi que jay dessus dit. Encores dit que ces portes batent par telle maniere quil est proprement advis à celuy qui y doit entrer que entrer ne pourroit sans estre entre deux cueilly et tout effroissie. Et ce fut la chose qui plus espouventa les deux allemans dessus diz...»].

Fig. 11 - The excerpt on the ever-slamming metal doors taken from folia 11r and 12r of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, preserved at the Bibliothèque du Château - Musée Condé in Chantilly

And in the printed edition of the same account, published in 1527 with the title *La Salade*, a frightful, additional detail is found: «... and wholly

crushed as a small fly» [«... et tout effroisse comme une mousche»] (Fig. 2).

Fig. 12 - The same passage on the magical doors as it appears in Antoine de la Sale's *La Salade*, printed in 1527 in Paris

Again, the power of de la Sale's storytelling is such that every reader, for centuries and centuries, has lingered over these words, dreaming of the cave and wishing to have a chance in life to get to the Sibyl's abode and meet the fairy lady, after having overcome the magical slamming device.

However, as we illustrated in our previous article *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl - The Literary Truth about the Magical Doors Set beneath Mount Sibyl*, such doors and devices are not new artifacts in ancient western literature. Antoine de la Sale took the doors from elsewhere and included them in his account of his visit to the Sibyl's cave.

And where did he borrowed them from? A first instance is found in chivalric literature.

As I already detailed in my article *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and His Forefathers: Huon of Bordeaux*, we find a similar device in an earlier, thirteenth-century epic poem, *Huon of Bordeaux*:

«Two men are standing at the gate; they are made of bronze, each man holding a double scourge, all made of metal and terror-inspiring. They never stop striking and lashing to and from, throughout summer and winter. In truth I tell you that no small bird, as quick as it may go flurrying about, would never be able to get into the palace without being killed; it would not succeed in getting through» [in the original French text: «Et s'a deux hommes à l'entrer de l'ostel; Tout sont de keuvre et fait et compasé, Si tient cascuns un flaiel acouplé, Tout sont de fer, moult font à redouter. Tout adès batent et yver et esté, Et si vous di, par fine verité, Une aloete, que bien tost set voler, Ne poroit mie ens el palais voler Que ne fust morte; ne poroit escaper»].

And that's not all. We find another instance of the same slamming contrivance in another earlier chivalric poem, *Huon d'Auvergne*, in a scene set by the castle of Lucifer (see my previous article *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and His Forefathers: Huon d'Auvergne*):

«A lofty palace, with a tower standing before it,
Not made of stone as towers are used to be made;
That is made of metal, and tempered iron;
High walls are around the palace,
A front gate guarded by two lions,
And the gate is such
That as soon as it is swung open,
No blade is as sharp as the gate itself,
the doors cutting easily and sweetly;
they just keep on opening up and shutting close».

[in the original French-Italian text:
«Alto è el pallaço, una tore davanti li à,
No è de piere como le tore se fa,
Ançy è d'açalle e de fero tenperà;
Alti son li muri ch'el palaço cricundà,
Davanti à una porta che do lion guardà,
E quele porte tal natura si à

Si tosto como elle averte incontenente se serà,
El non è raxori tanto taianti e filà
Che taia cossì soave como quele porte fa;
De serar e de avre alltro elle non fa».]

Here they are: in both *Huon de Bordeaux* and *Huon d'Auvergne* we find the very same revolving trap: a sharpened metal device protecting a fairy place, featuring a ceaseless motion across days and nights and summers and winters. A contrivance intended to unleash terror in the soul of the visitors (and the readers), with the same kind of small animals - birds or insects - used as an example of the crushing effect on the bold adventurers.

So Antoine de la Sale included a similar mechanism in his own account on the Sibyl's cave, a storyteller's trick drawn from chivalric literature intended to increase the thrill and enjoyment levels in his courtly audience.

But the lineage of all that - just like it was the case for the magical narrow bridge - is much older than that. The metal device, a rotating mechanism of such a kind that it never stops its evil gyration derives from a narrative we have already met before, the medieval Irish legend of St. Patrick. In the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, dating to the twelfth century, we actually find the following:

«He saw before him a huge wheel made of iron and fire, whose spokes and rim were entirely encircled with fiery hooks, to each of which single hanging men were stuck. [...] And the fiends [...] made the wheel go upwards. On the other side, other demons [...] pushed it downwards and made it turn around so quick that it was hardly visible» [in the original Latin text: «Vidit ante se maximam rotam ferream et igneam, cujus radii et canti unciis igneis undique erant circumfecti, in quibus singulis pendebant quasi homines infixi. [...] Demones igitur [...] rotam levaverunt. Alii ex alia parte [...] deorsum depresserunt tantaque eam agilitate fecerunt rotare, ut nullus omnino alium posset discernere»].

And we find other instances of such a narrative scheme, like in the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, an eleventh-century account written in the *Lebor na hUidre (Book of the Dun Cow)*, an ancient Irish manuscript. It contains very interesting special doors, protecting the entrance to the city of the Land of Saints:

«In the main doorway of the city they are confronted by a veil of fire and a veil of ice, smiting perpetually one against the other. The noise and din of these veils, as they clash together, are heard throughout the world, and the seed of Adam, should they hear that din, would be seized thereat with trembling and intolerable dismay».

[In the original Irish text: «Fíal tened ocus fíal d'aigriud i prímdorus inna cathrac inna fíadnaisse...»]

Other examples can be also found in the Arthurian cycle, such as the one retrieved in *The High History of the Holy Grail (Li Hauz Livres du Graal)*, a romance written in old French at the beginning of the thirteenth century. Let's read a remarkable passage in the text version taken from folium 86r of manuscript Français 1428 preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France:

«At the entrance to the gateway of the castle were two men made by art of necromancy, and they held two great mallets of iron, and so strongly they struck and hurt that nought is there in the world that might pass through amongst their blows but should be all to-crushed thereby. [... A Voice told him not to be afraid as] no power had they to harm such a knight as was he. He comforted himself much of that the Voice said to him. He comes near to the serjeants of copper, and they cease to strike at once, and hold their iron mallets quite still. And he entered into the castle».

[In the Old French text: «A l'entrée de la porte avoit ii omes fait par art de nigramance, si tenoient deus grans mas de fer, si s'acoupoient et feroient si très durement quyl n'est riens en le mond à peust passer parmi lor cox, que tot ne fust confunduz [... Une voix lui dit de ne pas s'épouvanter parce-que] il navoient pover de mal faire si bon chevalier qil estoiet. Il conforte mout en co que la voix dist; il proches des vileins de keuvre, et il targent de férir tantost se tienent de ferir tos coiz les max de fer; et il entre el chastel»].

As we showed in our previous article *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl - The Literary Truth about the Magical Doors Set beneath Mount Sibyl*, the original prototype of the magical, ever-moving barriers, the grim perilous passages that only true heroes can go through and overcome, is to be traced

back to ancient Greece: it's the Symplegades, the «ever-clashing cliffs» described by Apollonius of Rhodes in his epic poem *Argonautica*.

Fig. 13 - The episode of the necromantic mallets taken from *Li Hauz Livres du Graal* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Français 1428, folium 86r)

And that is the origin of the literary tradition concerning the magical, ever-slamming metal doors: a tradition which has ended up its long journey through history as a magical, thrilling element included in the narrative of a French gentleman, Antoine de la Sale, who was pleased to amaze his noble audience with an account concerning a fairy realm concealed beneath a remote Italian mountain. That same Antoine de la Sale who, with the last remarks contained in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, tells the reader that «I wrote all this [...] for the sake of amusement and to while away the hours» [In the original French text: «pour rire et passer temps [...] jay mis tout en escript»].

Those doors are now unhinged. They have nothing to do with the original core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend.

The flaws, in the myth of a Sibyl of the Apennines, widen and enlarge. The scent of a trail, leading the hunter away from the standard perception of this

lore and directing him towards the true core of the legend, becomes more and more evident.

Fig. 14 - Antoine de la Sale's remarks on the significance of his own account appearing at folium 27r of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*

Antoine de la Sale's doors, just like his narrow bridge, are just another disguise under which something different is concealed: a disguise that was borrowed from different, earlier traditions. We have to take it off if we want to get nearer to the original nucleus of Mount Sibyl's legend.

Nonetheless, we are not finished yet. There are still additions we still need to take off so that we can look at the true countenance of our Sibyl.

Let's see in the next article what else is to be removed from the Sibyl's face.

5. Sensual damsels, necromantic ladies, journeys to Rome and other familiar situations

Layer by layer, leave by leave, with this series of articles we are unfolding the antique literary envelope which for centuries has concealed the true semblance of the Apennine Sibyl: an operation we are carrying out by removing the narrative additions that actually belong to different legendary traditions.

After having ascertained that no mention of an Apennine Sibyl is to be retrieved in any available Roman or medieval text, we began our most delicate work by taking out the magical narrow bridge which, according to Antoine de la Sale, was part of the Sibyl's legend and lore. Subsequently,

we proceeded to remove from the sibilline tradition the ever-clashing metal doors, a device that was mentioned by de la Sale in connection to the Sibyl's cave.

What will our next step be?

We harbour a suspicion: that many other narrative elements contained in *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* may actually be taken or even copied from earlier romances, or poems. Especially chivalric romances and poems. Just like *Huon d'Auvergne* and *Huon of Bordeaux*, two examples of Middle-Ages works in which we found references to the magical bridge and the magical doors.

Are we on the right track? Yes, we are. We are going to find a number of literary references to episodes very similar to those reported by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale as to the Apennine Sibyl. The remarkable fact is that such references are contained in works that have nothing to do with the legend concerning Mount Sibyl.

Fig. 15 - The towering cliff of Mont Sibyl in the Italian Apennines

To begin with, let's stick to chivalric literature, and look at what happens when we open the pages of *Huon d'Auvergne*, the chivalric poem dating to a period set between the mid-fourteenth century and the beginning of the fifteenth century. As we already noted, for the first time ever, in a previous article (*The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and His*

Forefathers: Huon d'Auvergne), we stumble upon a literary scene that sounds so oddly familiar to our ears.

Fig. 16 - A portion of a page (folium 112r) from *Huon d'Auvergne* contained in manuscript n. 32 preserved at the Biblioteca del Seminario Vescovile in Padova

Huon is travelling near the river Tigris, when he meets three damsels. And here is what the three fair ladies say to him:

«You must be aware that our master
is a dame from the mountain.
Neither Medea nor Helen were so fair,
and no other woman was so wise in Britain;
She is proficient in black arts,
more than all the scholars in Toledo and Spain»

[in the original French-Italian text:
«Tu dé saver ch'el nostro capetaine
È una dame de ça da la montagne.
No fo si bela Medea ni Helaine,
Nian si savia fui in Bertagne;
De negromencia ella è sovraine,
Plui che no sé sença ingagne
Tuti li maistri de Toleta ni de Spagne»].

And they add: «she knows the language of necromancy - if you know how to ask and tell her [...] - you will be able to know how to go to Mount Hell»

[in the original French-Italian text: «de negromançia sa tuto lo latin - Se tu te saveré domandar e contar a lei ben vexin [...] - E può saver da lie tuto lo train - Como tu anderé al munte inferin»].

All of a sudden, something well known seems to appear: a «dame from the mountain», a wise queen, a necromancer who can deliver oracular responses to visitors, and send them to a «Mount Hell».

All this, though transferred by the banks of river Tigris, seems a portrait of a sort of Apennine Sibyl, the dame who Andrea da Barberino, in his romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, called the «wise Sibyl» («savia Sibilla» e «sapiantissima Sibilla» in Italian). And the correspondence appears to be even closer when we read *Huon's* description of the three young ladies:

«three damsels [...] Each one of them was remarkably handsome - their eyes sparkling and their cheeks most white - and as red as fresh roses - their slender arms on their beautiful shoulders - their breasts dancing before them» [in the original French-Italian text: «tre damissele [...] De gran beleça fo çascuna d'eles - Li so ochi à vari e blanche lor maseles - Color vermeio como ruoxe noveles - Sulle spale pendeano lor dreçe beles - Davanti lo sso peti ponceano le so mameles»].

But all this brings to our mind a similar scene we find in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch*, when the main character, in the recesses of the Sibyl's cave, knocks at a door flanked by two sculpted demons. When the door opens, three damsels appear:

«the three damsels were so handsome and perfectly shaped that no tongue will ever be able to depict their beauty» [in the original Italian text: «queste erano tre damiselle tanto polite e belle che lingua mai non lo potrebe dire tanto era la loro bellezza»].

Strange enough, different heroes (Huon, Guerrino) meet a same number of damsels in different places ruled by similar necromantic and oracular queens. And Guerrino's queen, the Sibyl, «shows him her own fairness and her white flesh, with her breasts which looked like polished ivory» [in the original Italian text: «mostrandoli la sua bellezza e le sue bianche carne e le mamelle che pareano proprio che fossero da volio»], which reminds us of the seductive qualities shown by the three damsels to Huon.

Fig. 17 - The excerpt on the three damsels taken from the printed edition of *Guerrino ditto Meschino* published in Venice in 1477

All this might just appear as some kind of commonplace coincidence between two chivalric works featuring brave heroes in search of fame and glory. However, the unlikely occurrences pile up one after another.

Huon d'Auvergne, just like Guerrino the Wretch, follows the young ladies to meet the necromantic queen. And we find a same spell acting on this hero, a close relative of the enchantment which is at work in the cave of the Apennine Sibyl: «the Devil was using all his powers - to lead him into wicked straits» [«che llo diavollo adoverave la sso possançe - de condurlo a malvasse sentançe»]. The spell of the magnificent castle he is led into is so powerful that Huon thinks to himself that «I would never go back to my Alvernia» («mai non curerav'io in Alvernia torner»).

Then, as we already saw for the first time in my previous article *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and His Forefathers: Huon d'Auvergne*, Huon is admitted to the presence of the queen («la raina») and his eyes behold a most beautiful woman; yet our valiant knight «knows for certain that her fairness was fake and illusory» («sapié per certaine - che sso belleça era falssa e vaine»). But the same applies to the Sibyls and her damsels, who are turned once a week into ugly beasts, serpents and vermins. The evil queen will try to lure Huon into sin - the same luxurious

sin as offered by the Apennine Sibyl to her visitors: and Huon will raise the very same anguished cry - «come to my aid, Jesus from Nazareth» [«Secori lo to servo, naçareno Jexhu»] - as Guerrino the Wretch will utter in despair in an identical occurrence in Andrea da Barberino's romance: «Jesus Christ from Nazareth save my soul» [«Iesu christo nazareno fame salvo»].

At last, both Huon and Guerrino actually succeed in preserving their own purity: they resist the enticements presented to them by their ghastly queens, so that all enchantments disappear and they can leave the magical kingdoms unblemished.

What happens next? If we want to find other astounding clues, let's turn our attention to another Huon, the thirteenth-century epic poem *Huon of Bordeaux*.

As we know, in Andrea da Barberino's chivalric romance, the main character Guerrino, after his stay in the Sibyl's cave, rides to Rome so as to ask the Pope for forgiveness:

Fig. 18 - Guerrino's journey to Rome from the printed edition of "Guerrino ditto Meschino" published in Venice in 1477

«He journeyed for many days heading to Rome. At the hotel he rested one day: then he went to St. Peter, and asked many people to have the chance to talk to the Holy Father [...] He knelt down to the Pope's feet, he kissed them while he wept, as he cried for forgiveness». [in the original Italian

text: «per molte giornate andò a Roma. A lo albergo se reposò uno giorno: poi andò a santo petro, e domandò a molti de parlare a lo santo padre [...] inzinchiose in sina ali soi pedi, e baxò li piedi sempre pianzendo, e cridando misericordia»].

And the same happens to a German knight in Antoine de La Sale's text, after a visit to the abode of the Sibyl:

«And when he arrived to Rome, with no hesitation, as soon as he could, he went to St. Peter. Then he threw himself at the feet of a priest [...] 'Holy Father, said the knight [...] I come to you, the Vicar of Christ, to beg for forgiveness and mercy». [in the original French text: «Et quant il fut à Romme, sans plus attendre, tant qu'il peult, en l'eglise Saint Pierre s'en va. Lors se gecta aux pieds d'ung penancier [...] 'Pere Sainct, dist le chevalier [...] je viens à vous, Vicaire de Dieu, pour requerir pardon et mercy»].

Fig. 19 - Antoine de la Sale's German knight before the Pope in the miniature from folium 17r of manuscript no. 0653 (0924) *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*

Is that an original idea conceived by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale? Absolutely not. Because we find a same scene written two centuries earlier in *Huon of Bordeaux*, as I already referenced in my previous article *The Knights of the Sibyl - Guerrino the Wretch and His Forefathers: Huon of Bordeaux*:

«They came to the city of Rome. That night they were housed in a hotel; they were much attended and honored. And the subsequent day, when the day came [...] they went to the monastery of St. Peter. The Pope was celebrating a high mass; Huon listened to it as well as his companions. When it was over and the celebrations had ended, and the Pope came back from the monastery, Huon walked toward him [...] He confessed all his sins to him» [in the original French text: «il sont venu à Romme le chité. Cele nuit sont herbegié à l'ostel; Moulit furent bien servi et honneré. Et l'endemain, quant il fu ajorné [...] au mostier Saint Piere en sont alé. Li apostoles faisoit messe canter; Hues l'escoute et se gent autretel. Quand dite fu et li mestiers finés, Et l'apostoles est du mostier tornés. Hues li est à son encontre alés [...] A lui s'est lues li enfes confesés»].

Again and again, we find narrative situations concerning Guerrino the Wretch which are actually present in earlier chivalric works. Situations that include, it is worth remembering, also narrow bridges and metal slamming or rotating devices, like the ones depicted by Antoine de la Sale.

But something even more striking occurs in *Huon of Bordeaux*. Do you remember when we reported that Huon of Bordeaux confronted with metal scourges ceaselessly lashing and whipping to prevent visitors from passing through? He succeeded in passing through them and then got into a magical castle.

In the castle, a lady bearing an utterly surprising name is waiting for him:

«The son of Sewin [Huon] from the town of Bordeaux, stroke three great blows on the golden basin [which stood beside the bronze guards]. A maiden in the castle listened to the resounding noise, her name was Sebile, a most handsome lady; as soon as the golden basin resounded, she went by a window and saw Huon who was trying to get in». [in the original French text: «Li fieus Sewins, de Bordiax la cité, Sour le bacin qui fu f'or esmeré a fru trois cos par moult grande fierté. Une pucele ou u palais listé, Sebile ot

nom, moult par ot de biauté; Si tost comme ot le bacin d'or sonner, A le fenestre s'en est venue ester, et voit Huon qui veut laiens entrer»].

Fig. 20 - The passage on Sebile in François Guessard's transcript of *Huon de Bordeaux* from manuscript n. 936 preserved at the Bibliothèque Municipale in Tours (France)

The magical castle hides a young lady: a lady whose name is «Sebile» - an ancient French spelling for the word 'Sibyl'.

Something is clearly wrong. We are detecting so many clues, so many links to other narrations that we are quite shocked.

There are chivalric romances, earlier than *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, that already contain episodes we later find in those two works. As if Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale did not refrain from drawing ideas and material from previous, already written literature.

This is actually no news in literary invention of all times. Nor is this to be considered as a sort of guilt. In chivalric literature, it actually occurs most frequently, owing to the networked circulation of narratives and episodes amid scribes and oral performers across Europe.

Nonetheless, it tells us something of the utmost importance: the matter of the Apennine Sibyl appears to be not completely original, because it is taken from different earlier literary sources. Some of them, as we have just seen, are chivalric poems and romances.

A dame, a necromantic power, an oracle. Living inside a castle, a cave, a magical place, protected by strange bridge and devices.

We find even an additional instance of that in *The High History of the Holy Grail* (*Li Hauz Livres du Graal*), a thirteenth-century romance we already quoted as containing two ever-striking iron mallets protecting a magical castle. Inside the castle, we find once more something that we already know:

«There was an evil spirit within that gave answers concerning any matter they wanted to hear of» («avoit malvais esperiez dedens qui lor donoit respons de canque il voloient oir»).

Fig. 21 - The evil oracle from *Li Hauz Livres du Graal* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Français 1428, folium 86r)

Something inside. That rendered oracular response to its visitors. An evil spirit that seems to be very similar to an Apennine Sibyl. And protected by a very similar ever-moving device.

But did Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale know such chivalric poems and romances? Of course they did. As we noted before, de la Sale was a man of letters and an experienced courtier. Andrea da Barberino did

something even more conclusive: at the end of the fourteenth century he wrote an Italian translation of *Huon d'Auvergne*: a romance whose title is *Ugone d'Avernia*, a sort of *Guerrino the Wretch* containing Huon's deeds and adventures, even though greatly expanded if compared to the original manuscripts of *Huon d'Auvergne*.

Again, it seems that we have found new leaves which shelter the true essence of the Apennine Sibyl's legend, leaves that need removal: chivalric additions that are encountered in various preceding texts, suitably re-used by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale later in time to confer more literary spice to their own works.

Let's take a closer look to such leaves, in an effort to take them out as thoroughly as we can.

To perform that task, we will urge one of our most illustrious author into a very special arena. We are going to attend a truly astounding fight: Andrea da Barberino vs. Andrea da Barberino himself.

We will compare selected excerpts from *Guerrino the Wretch* with specific passages drawn from *Ugone d'Avernia*. And we will behold amazing deeds.

6. Chivalric additions to the Sibyl's legend

The more we proceed into a deeper analysis of the Apennine Sibyl's currently known legendary narration, the more we find additional literary layers that enshroud the inner core of the legend and disguise the true semblance of our Sibyl.

We have started to walk with hesitant steps amid chivalric romances and poems, and what we are stumbling upon is quite upsetting: we begin to retrieve sparse references to episodes we already know within the framework of such works as *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, yet they refer to different literary situations and circumstances, featuring different heroes, different settings and different villains.

This means that many of the episodes which are part of the Apennine Sibyl's legend and lore originate from other sources, and are rooted in an antique chivalric literary lineage. Such episodes have been used by authors like Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, and by a plethora of unknown storytellers, oral performers and jongleurs before their noble and popular audiences, but have actually nothing to do with the original myth concerning the cave and lake existing on the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy.

Let's make some further steps along this perilous, vertiginous research trail. We are now going to consider Andrea da Barberino's version of the ancient French-Italian narration of *Huon d'Auvergne*.

Andrea da Barberino, the author of *Guerrino the Wretch*, was also the author of a number of additional chivalric romances: *Huon d'Auvergne*, *The History of Ajolfus of Barbicon and Other Valiant Knights*, *The Royal House of France*, *Narbonnais Chronicles*, *The Aspromonte*: tales of valiant knights, epic deeds, virginal damsels, far-away countries, evil beasts, ghastly monsters, and magical visions, not so dissimilar from our best-known romance *Guerrino the Wretch*. Drawing on an illustrious tradition of chivalric literature written in French, Andrea da Barberino took many of such romances and translated them into Italian. Not a mere translator's work was his literary production, as his prose was intended for long sessions of reading before a captivated audience: a huge amount of additional narrative elements was always included in his revised, widely enlarged romances, featuring hundreds and hundreds of pages and made up by an almost ceaseless sequence of chivalric episodes, the vast majority of which depicting a fight between the main character and hero, and any kind of opponent - be it a knight, a king, a loathsome snake, a wild lion, or a demon.

In this immense ocean of material, we retrieve a few literary images we have already come into: images we have read in *Guerrino the Wretch*.

Let's take *Ugone d'Avernia*, whose manuscript is preserved at the Florence National Central Library as the Magliabechian Codex Cl. VI.81.P.III, no. 59, edited by Zambrini / Bacchi Della Lega in 1882: a work in excess of six hundred pages, full to the brim of the many deeds accomplished by Huon, the hero who is depicted in the earlier French-Italian romance *Huon*

d'Auvergne, transformed by Andrea da Barberino into the main character of a much longer and intricated narrative.

Fig. 22 - The opening and ending remarks of Andrea da Barberino's *Ugone d'Avernia* from manuscript Magliabechian Cl. VI.81.P.III, no. 59 preserved at the Florence National Central Library, as transcribed by F. Zambrini and A. Bacchi della Lega in 1882

What do we find in Andrea da Barberino's "Ugone"?

Perhaps the reader remembers that in Padua's manuscripted version of *Huon d'Auvergne*, we found an episode set by the banks of the river Tigris and concerning three damsels, who introduced Huon to a realm ruled by a «dame from the mountain», proficient in necromancy: a dame who appeared to show a remarkable resemblance to Guerrino's Apennine Sibyl, as depicted by Andrea da Barberino, even though the scene from *Huon* was not set in a cavern.

Did Andrea da Barberino copied his wicked Sibyl from the necromantic dame which appears in *Huon d'Auvergne*? Maybe. Yet, he might as well have copied straight from himself. Because the very same episode is also

contained in his *Ugone d'Avernia*, and this time it is set by the course of river Nile, with Huon in search of a way to reach the entrance to Hell (Chapter XXXVIII):

«How it happened that Huon met three damsels, who danced and singed, and who were evil spirits - Huon journeyed for ten days up the river [...] he saw a beach with three damsels, who in the woods, under the shadowy trees, were singing a French song [... Huon] steered the ship to the river's bank and said to himself: I do want to see what sort of adventure this may turn out to be! [...] And then the third damsel said: now I'll tell you about who we are. Know then that our master is a lady, beyond that mountain; that she is handsome and wise, more than anybody else; and she is the best necromancer in the world; and know that if you come to her, she will show you and teach you the way to meet your goal [... here is] a town, more valuable than any other one in the world, and here all pleasures that can be enjoyed by a mortal men, they can be obtained, and flavoured food, and gardens, and other scented fruit. [...] So I tell you, if you come and see the beautiful dame, and the pleasant waters, you will not be able to leave».

Fig. 23 - The excerpt on the negromantic lady contained in Andrea da Barberino's *Ugone d'Avernia*

[In the original Italian text: «Come Ugo arrivò a tre dame, che ballavano e sonavano, ch'erano spiriti maligni - Andò Ugone, dipoi dieci giorni, su pel fiume [...] vidde in una spiaggia tre damigelle, che nel bosco, all'ombra degli alberi, cantavano una canzonetta franciosa [... Ugone] menò la nave alla riva, dicendo: io voglio vedere che aventura è questa! [...] e dipoi disse la terza: ora ti vorrò [dire] di nostro affare. Sappi, che nostro signore è una

dama, passata quella montagna; ch'è bella e saggia, più che niun'altra che sia; ed è la migliore negromanta del mondo; e sappi, che se tu vieni a lei, ed ella ti potrà mostrare, e insegnare il modo che tu fornirai la tua bisogna [... qui è] una città, che tutte l'altre del mondo non vagliano, quanto questa sola, et qui tutti i dilette che per uomo mortale si può avere [sono], e spezierie, e giardini, ed altri odoriferi frutti. [...] e ciò ti dico, se tu vieni a vedere la bella dama, e le belle acque, tu non te ne saprai partire».]

Again, in a romance different from *Guerrino the Wretch*, we find a situation which strongly reminds us of the Sibyl's adventure and cave, described by the same author, Andrea da Barberino. We have a necromantic lady, to whom the main hero is introduced by three charming damsels, and the lures they present to him include a superb town and gardens and food, not dissimilar by the magical visions described by Andrea da Barberino as on show within the subterranean realm of the Sibyl. Visions which unleash on the unwary visitor the very same effects: the weakening of any willingness to leave that enchanted place and go back home.

And the available delights, too, seem to be quite the same: «the Sibyl came with all that pleasures and entertainments that are achievable by a human body», says Andrea da Barberino in *Guerrino the Wretch* [in the original Italian text: «la Sibila vene con tuti quelli piaceri e ziochi che fosse possibile che a uno corpo humano se potesse fare»].

The title of Chapter XXXIX in the *Ugone d'Avernia* leaves us with only minor doubts: «How it happened that Huon went to the ladies of the fake town, who were but demons who wanted to ensnare him» [in the original Italian text: «Come Ugone andò dalle dame della città contraffatta alla reina, che erano tanti diavoli che lo volevano ingannare»]. The episode seems to take on the very same colours and patterns of Guerrino's visit to the sibilline cave in *Guerrino the Wretch*, when our hero «saw many castles and mansions and palaces and many gardens, and he imagined all that be witchcraft: for in such a small place within the mountain it was unfeasible that so many buildings were there» [in the original Italian text: «vide molte castelle e molte ville molti palacii e molti ziardini et imaginò questi tutti essere incantamenti: per che in poco loco de la montagna non era possibile che tante cose vi fosseno»].

Because Huon is brought to a town with «all the walls made of marble, carved with sculpted figures [... and] all the charming gardens» [in the original Italian text: «tutte le mura di marmo, storiato di rilevate figure [... e] tutti i bei giardini»], a description which is really close to that presented in *Guerrino the Wretch*, when Guerrino first get into the Sibyl's realm: «they came to a large garden and a most charming loggia completely carved» [in the original Italian text: «zionzeno a uno grando ziardino a una bellissima lozia tuta istoriata»]. Note that Andrea da Barberino makes use of the same Italian word «istoriato» («carved, adorned with carvings») to depict the richness and attractiveness of the place.

The moment when Huon meets his wise dame, and Guerrino his Sibyl, are very, very similar to each other:

Fig. 24 - The hero meets the fairy queen in *Ugone d'Avernia* (left) and *Guerrin Meschino* (right)

«Huon saw the queen and her damsels sitting in a chair of astounding craft; they were so beautiful that no comparison could never be possible, if they had truly been human beings. Huon saluted her with kindness; and she greeted him in turn, and stood up, and took Huon by his hand, and said: welcome to this man, a good and gentle knight!» [in the original Italian text: «e' trovò la reina e le donne sedere in una sedia di maravigliosa adornezza; tanto bella, che non ci è comparazione, s'elle fossono state corpo umano. Ugo la salutò gentilmente; ed ella gli rendé suo saluto, e levossi da sedere, e prese Ugo per la mano, dicendo: ben sia venuto questo uomo, da bene e gentile cavaliere!»].

«Amid them there was a most charming woman, the most beautiful Guerrino's eyes had ever beheld; and one of the three damsels said that its dame Sibyl and they went to her and she was coming towards them; and when Guerrino was before her he kneeled: and she kneeled too and took him by his hand and said welcome to Sir Guerrino» [in the original Italian text: «in mezo de quele era una bella donna più che lo ochii soi mai havesse veduto; et una de queste tre li disse quella è madonna la Sibilla et in verso lei andono et lei veniva in verso loro: et zionto apreso lei se inzinocchiò Guerino: e lei se inchinò e presolo per la mano et disse ben vegna mesere Guerino»].

The episode of the necromantic lady in *Ugone d'Avernia* is much shorter than the corresponding episode of the Sibyl in *Guerrino the Wretch*. However, in both romances the hero is lured into sin by the queen of the place, and in both works the main character calls for the divine protection to save his immortal soul:

«Huon, almost lost, cried out: come to my aid, to the aid of your servant, Jesus of Nazareth!» [in the original Italian text: «Ugone quasi smarrito, gridò: soccorrimi, servo tuo, Nazareno Iesù!»].

«[Guerrino] was about to fall; yet he came back to God and said thrice Jesus Christ of Nazareth set me free from those whichcrafts» [in the original Italian text: «saria caduto; ma tornato a dio disse tre volte Iesu christo nazareno libera me da questi incantamenti»].

Fig. 25 - Hugo (above) and Guerrino (Below) raise a same invocation to God when lured into sin

Even though the episodes found in *Ugone d'Avernia* and *Guerrino the Wretch* are not identical, it is apparent that some strict relationship exists

between the two: a connection which is not limited to a mere, casual resemblance to be ultimately ascribed to a common chivalric kinship.

And the supposedly 'casual' resemblances are not over. There is more to it. Let's see the additional, astounding similarities in the next article.

7. More chivalric additions to the Sibyl's legend

We are probing into the enigma of the origin of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, the mysterious oracle and prophetess who, since the fifteenth century, seems to inhabit a remote peak raising in the Apennine mountains, at the very center of the Italian peninsula. And the more we proceed in our investigation, the more we retrieve narrative episodes which seems to have been taken from earlier medieval romances: a sort of shelter which veils the true core of the legend, an envelope made up by a succession of leaves that are not truly pertinent to the fundamental essence of the Sibyl of the Apennines.

Fig. 26 - A vision of Mount Sibyl at sunset

Let's consider another astounding correspondence contained in Chapter LXVI of *Ugone d'Avernia*, which - once again - resounds in our ears as something we already know:

«How it happened that Huon, after a long walk, stumbled upon three hermits [...] and after having walked a full day, he saw a hollowed cave, a cavern, in which three men lived [...] those from the inside [...] all took a cross in their hands, and appealed to Huon with the following words: we beg you, in the name of Jesus Christ, not to do any harm to us [...] and welcomed him with great expressions of joy [...] This mountain has a name, said the eldest among them, on this mountain was stranded the Noah's Ark after the Flood» [in the original Italian text: «Come Ugo, caminato alquanto, trovò tre romiti [...] e quando fu ito una giornata, vide in una grotta forata una caverna, dove dimoravano tre uomini [...] quegli di drento [...] presono tutti una croce in mano, e iscongiurarono Ugo, così dicendo: io ti scongiuro, per lo nome di Iesù Cristo, che a noi non possa nuocere [...] e ricolsonlo con grandissima festa [...] Questa montagna s'appella, disse il maggiore di loro; in su questa montagna rimase l'arca di Noè per diluvio»].

a gridare: è nessuno qua dentro? io, nel nome di Dio Iesù Cristo, vi richieggo; io non v'inganno, io sono un Cristiano. Quando quegli di drento intesono e udirono, al nome di Dio, furono assai godenti e lieti, perchè erano stati assai lungo tempo che non avevano veduto uomo niuno; e presono tutti una croce in mano, e iscongiurarono Ugo, così dicendo: io ti scongiuro, per lo nome di Iesù Cristo, che a noi non possa nuocere; se tu sei buona cosa, vieni avanti a noi in buon'ora. Il Conte rispuose: sia come tu hai detto. A queste parole i tre romiti si fecero a lui, e ricolsonlo con

gradeza. Se conuene andare apicando p' la piu parte con le mane i certi falliti: cui li uole andare. hora dice el Meschino quando zōfeno a questo remitorio erano stanchi e bateno a luffo e smorono da caualo. Et uno de li Remiti respole: e disse. ihesuf nazarenuf tu ci aiuti. Sēti no comenzare cō grāde reuerentia: Deuf iadiutoriū meū intende. e ueneno a luffo cō questo sono. Et erano tre remiti ognihō auea una crozza i mano. E scōzirono uno de loro e disse: tornate idietro maledeti

Fig. 27 - The excerpts on the hermits as found in *Ugone d'Avernia* (left), from the as transcript edited by Zambrini / Bacchi della Lega, and *Guerrino the Wretch* (right), from the edition printed in Venice in 1477

Three hermits, a cross in their hands. And here is a similar passage, retrieved in the initial part of the sibilline episode described by Andrea da Barberino in “Guerrino the Wretch”:

«when they came to this hermitage they were tired [...] and one of the hermits answered to them, and said Jesus of Nazareth help us [...] and they were three hermits and each one of them had a small cross in his hand. And one of them pleaded them and said: go back [...] They were allowed in the hermitage together with their horses» [in the original Italian text: «Quando zonzeno a questo remitorio erano stanchi [...] et uno de li Remiti respose: e disse ihesus nazarenus tu ci aiuti [...] et erano tre remiti ogni homo avea una crosetta in mano. E sconzurone uno de loro e disse: tornate indrieto [...] Li misseno dentro loro e soi cauali»].

And we find a comparable episode in *I Reali di Francia (The Royal House of France)*, a fifteenth-century romance by the same author, Andrea da Barberino. Amid the innumerable events narrated in this lengthy romance, here is a hermit again:

«In the middle of the thick woods of Corneto [between Latium and Tuscany] he got lost and went about for three nights and two days, getting farther and farther through those forests, the third day he arrived to a Hermitage; he knocked at the door, and a hermit came out and shouted at him, evil Thief, you are to meet your own death. Fiovo bowed, and said. Oh Blessed man, I am no Thief, for I descend from a noble lineage [...] When the Hermit listened to his words [...] he said. Friend, I have nothing to eat, if God does not send any food to us, so let's take your horse to a place in which the wild beasts shall not devour it [...] and then they entered the Hermitage, and the Hermit signed himself with the Cross and blessed Fiovo»].

[in the original Italian text: «per le folte selve di Corneto si smarrì, et andò tre notti, e due giorni avviluppandosi per quelle selve, il terzo giorno arrivò la sera ad un Romitorio, et picchiato all'uscio, venne fuori un Romito, e gridò malvaggio Ladrone, alla morte sei venuto. Fiovo s'inchinò, e disse. O Santo huomo, io non son Ladrone, ma sono di gentil lignaggio [...] Quando il Romito l'intese [...] disse. Amico, io non ho da mangiare, se Dio non ce ne manda, ma mettiamo il cavallo in luogo, che le fiere non lo divorano [...] e dipoi entrarono nel Romitorio, e'l Romito fatto il segno della Croce, benedisse Fiovo»].

dosi per quelle selue, il terzo giorno arriuò la fera ad vn Romitorio, & picchiato all'uscio, venne fuori vn Romito, & gridò maluaggio Ladrone, alla morte sei venuto. Fiuou s'inchinò, e disse. O Santo huomo, io non son Ladrone, ma sono di gentil lignaggio, e si mi trouo perduto per questi boschi, e già sono passati tre giorni, ch'io non hò mangiato: onde io ti prego per amor di Dio, che mi aiuti in questa mia necessità, che Iddio ti rimeriterà per me. Quando il Romito l'intese, e pose mente à gli atti suoi, gli venne pietà, & hebbe di lui compassione, & disse. Amico, io non hò da mangiare, se Dio non ce ne manda, ma mettiamo il cauallo in luogo, che le fiere non lo diuorano, e misselo doue teneua ancor il suo cauallo, ilquale era magro, e dipoi entrarono nel Romitorio, c'l Romito fatto il segno della Croce, benedisse Fiuou, e poi domandò chi

Fig. 28 - The excerpt on the hermit as found in Andrea da Barberino's *I Reali di Francia* from the edition printed in Venice in 1674

This is a further demonstration of the fact that the hermits we find in the sibilline episode contained in *Guerrino the Wretch* are just a commonplace theme typical of chivalric literature, so much so that Andrea da Barberino liked to use hermits at least thrice in three different romances, and in situations that are remarkably similar.

Again, just a mere chance? It is manifest that specific literary themes have made their journey from *Ugone d'Avernia* to *Guerrino the Wretch*, and possibly also the other way round. There are many elements that are most likely been copied by Andrea da Barberino from one work to the other, and, for the sake of our search, it does not matter which one is the original source.

If we look for other instances, we may note that in Chapter XIII of Andrea da Barberino's *Ugone d'Avernia* the main character makes his way to Rome, while engaged in a quest to find the entryway to Hell, to meet the Pope: exactly the same situation we find in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapter CLVII), in which it's the Pope himself who tells Guerrino to go the Purgatory of St. Patrick («lo purgatorio de santo

Patritio» in Italian), the legendary Irish access point to Hell. Also remember that we found a similar occurrence in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* and in the thirteenth-century epic poem *Huon of Bordeaux*.

Fig. 29 - The knight hero visiting the Pope in Andrea da Barberino's *Ugone d'Avernia*

And now another significant example. In the *Ugone d'Avernia*, Ugo moves to the Italian province of Calabria in search of information on where to find an access to Hell:

«As he travelled through Calabria, and as he went about asking, the way I already told you, he found a few good men, who told him that he would find people able to help him in Athens; and many others corroborated the said assertions, by saying that there he would find many highly experienced men, mainly in the necromantic arts» [in the original Italian text: «et passando per la Calavria, et domandando, com'io v'ho detto, trovò alcuni uomini da bene, i quali gli dissono, che in Attene potrebbe trovare chi l'aiuterebbe di tal fatto; et per molti fu rafferma, perché v'erano valenti uomini esperti, e spezialmente in atto di negromanzia»].

Oddly enough, a same scene is present in *Guerrino the Wretch*:

«And he travelled to the kingdom of Calabria [...] He stayed in Reggio di Calabria for five days asking of that Sibyl. [...] While he was in the town of Reggio he happened to ask certain people about the location of the

mountain of the Sibyl; and he was with an elderly man who [...] said [...] that the mountains where the Sibyl is are in the middle of Italy» [in the original Italian text: «e vene al regno di Calauria [...] Stete a rezio [Reggio di Calabria] v giorni domandando de questa Sibilla. [...] Essendo Meschino in la città de rezio domandò certe persone dove era il monte de la Sibilla; et trouose con un homo uechio el quale [...] disse [...] che le montagne dove è la Sibila è in mezo de Italia»].

Another accidental occurrence? Yet now we start to have in our hands too many of them.

We can even find another one.

Let's consider a specific passage in *Guerrino the Wretch*, Andrea da Barberino's fifteenth-century romance which played a decisive role in spreading the Apennine Sibyl's legend throughout Europe. In Chapter CLIV, Guerrino, the valiant knight who met the Sibyl in her own enchanted den set beneath the hollow Italian mountain, despairs of having any chance to ever leave the evil abode of the prophetess, owing to the labyrinthine structure («uno grande lambarinto» in the original Italian text) of the oracle's dark cave.

sempre a Dio si raccomandava. Et passando per la Calavria, et domandando, com'io v'ho detto, trovò alcuni uomini da bene, i quali gli dicono, che in Attene potrebbe trovare chi l'aiuterebbe di tal fatto; et per molti fu rafferma, perchè v'erano valenti uomini esperti, e specialmente in atto di negromanzia. Per la qual cosa Ugone deliberò fare a questo modo; et venne al porto di Calavria, per trovare una nave che lo portasse in Attene, et trovò alla riva una galea che voleano partire d'ora in ora, et volevano andare in Albania. Questa si era una galea di corsari, nè ad

Italia: e per ritrovarle le montagne de la fuita sibilla. E da messina passò el faro: e uene al regno de Calauria la qual città fo fatta da una altra città: la quale era zofo nelo piano a pie de Arezio che se chiama risana. Li africani nel tempo de agolarè la disseveno. E po fo fatto Reozio. Et era allora una murata de nouo. Stete a rezio. v. zioeni domandando de questa Sibilla. E fu li dito como la iera i li monti de pinino in lo mezo de Italia sopra una città chiamata Norza. alcuni dicono come la e chiamata norza, ma i tuto questo libro e scripto Norza.

Essendo M. i la città de rezio: domando certe persone doue era il monte de la Sibilla. Et trouose con un hō uechio: el quale fu la piazza de Rezio i presencia de certi forestieri raxonando disse: che lui hauea un certo librezolo: chi plana de questa Sibilla. e como doi li erano adate: lūo nō uolse irare. e laltro intro. Quello che ritorno disse: che quele montagne erano gradi derupamēte: nō se habitauāo. E che le montagne doue e la Sibila: e i mezo de Italia doue sono tuti ueti. peche sono alte. e za li stauāo li griffoni.

Fig. 30 - The hero travels to the Italian province of Calabria from Andrea da Barberino's *Ugone d'Avernia* (left) and Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (right)

How can Guerrino succeed in his search for a way out? Incredibly enough, help will come to him from an utterly unexpected way. One of the Sibyl's fairy damsels will show him the position of the door leading to the external air and sun:

«A damsel came to him and said: O knight, you forgot that we are forced by God's Providence to show to you the time and place in which you are required to leave, so forget not and come with me, so I shall show you the gate and the way out of this abode».

[In the original Italian text: «Vene alui una damizella e disse o caualiero perche te desmentegi forza e a noi per la divina prouidencia demonstrarte lhora el ponto che tu dei usire e pero non te desmentigare e vieni apresso a mi che io te mostraro la porta e lusita de questa habitatione»].

Fig. 31 - A damsel of the Sibyl's retinue helps Guerrino in *Guerrino the Wretch*, from the edition printed in Venice in 1477

This excerpt might simply appear as a meaningless instance of an awkward decision in storytelling, with the romance's author just introducing an unrealistic trick to drive his knight out of trouble.

However, there is more to it.

Let's browse the vellum leaves of manuscript Français 1447 preserved at the Département des Manuscrits of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France. It contains *Claris et Laris*, a chivalric poem dating to the second half of the thirteenth century. In it, we find an episode involving the two main characters, the brave knights Claris and Laris. They both are held as prisoners in a magical castle, as we will see in more detail in a next article. How do they find their way out?

Needless to say, a helping hand comes from the inside, this time out of love:

«Madoine the fay woke up - And to the garden she went - [...] She took Laris by his right hand, - and brought him with her, - She showed a stone to him, - [...] Sir, she said, this stone - seals from here the way out; - By enchantment it was open - [...] So they went out across the countryside».

[In the original Italian text: «Madoine la fee iert levee - Et dedenz le jardin entree - [...] prist Laris par la main destre, - D'une part l'amaine en un estre, - Une pierre li a moustree, - [...] Sire, fet ele, cele pierre - Clot de ceanz la voie entiere; - Par nigromance fu ouvree - [...] Einsi s'en vont par la champaigne»].

Fig. 32 - The fine opening miniature of *Claris et Laris* from manuscript Français 1447 preserved at the Département des Manuscrits of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, with the passage on the knight heroes being helped in their escape by a fay who is part of the retinue of a magical castle (folia 92r, 92v and 93r)

In this passage, a fay shows an imprisoned knight the way out from a bewitched place of confinement: the very same situation we already saw in *Guerrino the Wretch*, a romance written nearly a hundred fifty years after *Claris et Laris*.

And we also have another example, with a different knight and a different fay.

If we consider *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, a French romance contained in manuscript Add. 10293 preserved at the British Library in London and dating to the early fourteenth century, we see the most famous knight Lancelot, a main character of the Arthurian cycle, held captive in a castle ruled by three magical ladies we will soon get to know better. And here is how the brave hero escapes the nasty grip of the enchantresses:

«So the damsel who took care of him came in - And when she saw him suffer so much she was very sorry - [...] I will lead you out of this prison at night - and I will provide you with good horse and weapons - [...] and then she said - Sir, come with me - And he rose and followed her - [...] Then he mounted his horse, the one the damsel had readied for him and then she bade him farewell - [...] So he left - and went out through the garden and then across a grassland».

[In the original French text: «Atant vient auant la damoisele qui de lui se prenoit garde - Et quant elle li voit tel doel demener si en fu trop dolante - [...] ie vous geteroie anuit hors de ceste prison - et vous donroie bon cheval et bones armes - [...] et li dist - Sire uenes apres moi - Et il se lieue et le sieut - [...] Los monte sou son cheval que la pucele liot fet apareillier et puis le commande a dieu - [...] Si sen part atant - et sen issi par i uergier et puis entre en vne praerie»].

Guerrino the Wretch, Claris and Laris, Lancelot: all of them are held in magical prisons; all of them are eventually freed by damsel belonging to the retinue of one or more dark ladies, who had confined those knights. The same narrative scheme is manifestly applied to very different casts and characters. And Guerrino the Wretch is just the last in time.

What should we think of all that?

Fig. 33 - The episode of Lancelot and a damsel contained in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Add. 10293 preserved at the British Library in London), with a miniature portraying the two characters (folium 281v) and the excerpts which describe Lancelot's escape from the magical castle (folia 282r and 282v)

The most important result of our investigation is that a number of single episodes contained in the sibilline portion of *Guerrino the Wretch* are taken from, or have contributed to, different romances, including *Ugone d'Avernia*: this means that the elements used in such romances are of literary, chivalric origin. All of them can be used in an interchangeable way, and can be transposed by the author or the oral performer into one work or the other, and just re-used with major or minor modifications, with the aim to stun, amuse and entertain an audience looking for knightly deeds and fairy adventures.

The final conclusion is straightforward: all such chivalric elements do not seem to pertain to the true core of the legendary tale of the Apennine Sibyl. In the narrative contained in *Guerrino the Wretch* concerning a Sibyl of the Apennines, there are elements we need to remove, if we want to get to the very essence of the sibilline legend.

The path we are now treading is very slippery. However, we are fully determined to clean the legend of all concentric layers that suffocate the real mythical nucleus.

And the next, painful step might be the removal, or some sort of a radical transformation, of the Sibyl herself.

Let's go and see why we should finally make up our minds and venture into this perilous, hazardous trail.

8. A new perspective in research

In our exploration of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, we are stumbling upon layers and layers of additional material: literary elements pertaining to different legendary traditions and tales which seem to have been superimposed to a basic mythical core connected to the presence of a sinister cave and lake in the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a remote, craggy territory set in the Italian central Apennines.

We discovered that a magical bridge and a bewitched door described by Antoine de la Sale as part of the sibilline legend are drawn from earlier narratives of visits to the Otherworld.

We found out that an episode concerning a visit of a knight to a sensual necromantic lady living by a mountain and concealing her true nature as an evil demon is contained in an earlier poem, *Huon d'Auvergne*. We also noted that a certain number of situations described by Andrea da Barberino in his *Guerrino the Wretch*, including an encounter with three damsels, an invocation to Jesus, and a journey to Rome to see the Pope, are also present in other medieval works.

And when we took in our hands different works written by the same Andrea da Barberino, we stumbled upon other similar episodes, such as the encounter with the hermits, the search for information in the Italian province of Calabria, and the whole episode concerning the visit to a nasty queen in *Ugone d'Avernia*.

All of that, in addition to the fact that no reference to an Apennine Sibyl can be found in both Roman and medieval literary traditions before the beginning of the fifteenth century, seems to suggest that we should now take a perilous, treacherous turn in our most fascinating, yet formidable enquiry.

We are going to investigate the literary traces of the presence of necromantic ladies and evil queens and prophesying Sibyls in the medieval tradition and literature.

Why are we doing so? Because our search might ultimately lead to an apparently unpleasant, almost unwanted conclusion: the Apennine Sibyl is not an original feature of our mythical tale, as most probably she was just superimposed to the true, fundamental core of the legend concerning the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 34 - Italy and the enigma of Mount Sibyl

We are envisaging, with faltering, uneasy steps, a legend of the Apennine Sibyl with no Sibyl in it.

A final, definitive loss? The cancellation of a most illustrious legend and dream? The ultimate, sad outcome of a rigorous, unyielding investigation based on the analysis of literary sources and original manuscripts?

Not at all. We will see that the tale's original core, the mythical might of the legend was already there before a Sibyl came. And still is.

Before discussing the meaning and reach of such apparently preposterous statements, let's venture into this long, winding, slippery trail.

9. A queen who presides over an enchanted realm (but she is not the Apennine Sibyl)

As we have shown in the preceding articles, we know that the Apennine Sibyl's cavern is not the one and only literary instance of a secure, concealed place, often located on a mountain, adorned with beautiful gardens and magnificent palaces, and inhabited by a malign entity, often a sort of dark lady.

We saw that a similar necromantic queen lives in a magical castle in the French poem *Huon d'Auvergne*:

«You must be aware that our master
is a dame from the mountain [...]
and no other woman was so wise in Britain;
She is proficient in black arts [...]
she knows the language of necromancy
if you know how to ask and tell her [...]
you will be able to know how to go to Mount Hell»

[in the original French-Italian text:

«Tu dé saver ch'el nostro capetaine
È una dame de ça da la montagne [...]
Nian si savia fui in Bertagne;
De negromencia ella è sovraine [...]
de negromançia sa tuto lo latin

Se tu te saveré domandar e contar a lei ben vexin [...]
E può saver da lie tuto lo train
Como tu anderé al munte inferin»].

And the same we find in Andrea da Barberino's *Ugone d'Avernia*:

«Know then that our master is a lady, beyond that mountain; that she is handsome and wise, more than anybody else; and she is the best necromancer in the world; and know that if you come to her, she will show you and teach you the way to meet your goal [... here is] a town, more valuable than any other one in the world, and here all pleasures that can be enjoyed by mortal men [...] you will not be able to leave».

[In the original Italian text: «Sappi, che nostro signore è una dama, passata quella montagna; ch'è bella e saggia, più che niun'altra che sia; ed è la migliore negromanta del mondo; e sappi, che se tu vieni a lei, ed ella ti potrà mostrare, e insegnare il modo che tu fornirai la tua bisogna [... qui è] una città, che tutte l'altre del mondo non vagliano, quanto questa sola, et qui tutti i dilette che per uomo mortale si può avere [sono] [...], tu non te ne saprai partire».]

An additional instance is found in the castle described by *The High History of the Holy Grail (Li Hauz Livres du Graal)*, a thirteenth-century romance:

«There was an evil spirit within that gave answers concerning any matter they wanted to hear of» (in the old French text: «avoit malvais esperiez dedens qui lor donoit respons de canque il voloient oir»).

Another example is found in *Huon of Bordeaux*, the thirteenth-century epic poem. Within the castle protected by magically striking metal scourges we already saw that a lady is found whose name - strange enough - is Sibyl:

«The son of Sewin [Huon] from the town of Bordeaux, stroke three great blows on the golden basin [which stood beside the bronze guards]. A maiden in the castle listened to the resounding noise, her name was Sebile, a most handsome lady; as soon as the golden basin resounded, she went by a window and saw Huon who was trying to get in». [in the original French text: «Li fieus Sewins, de Bordiax la cité, Sour le bacin qui fu f'or esmeré a fru trois cos par moult grande fierté. Une pucele ou u palais listé, Sebile ot

nom, moult par ot de biauté; Si tost comme ot le bacin d'or sonner, A le fenestre s'en est venue ester, et voit Huon qui veut laiens entrer»].

No one of such ladies or enchanters, in the literary works they are drawn from, is the Sibyl of the Apennines. No one of them lives under an Italian Mount Sibyl. No one of them has nothing to do with Guerrino the Wretch or is mentioned in the travel account by Antoine de la Sale. They live their literary, fictional lives elsewhere.

What does it all mean? What kind of dark lady, featuring some strange connection to the name 'Sibyl/Sebile', is hidden behind all those references and mentions?

As a matter of fact, throughout the Middle Ages the idea of a hidden, enchanted realm, inhabited by some kind of being and containing all sort of magical wonders, is not an exclusive feature of the Apennine Sibyl's legend.

But the utterly astounding thing is the fact that, as we are about to ascertain, in this same ruling role other remarkable names sometime appear. And they appear centuries before the works by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale were written.

Let's open the pages of *Claris et Laris*, a chivalric poem which is dated by scholars to the second half of the thirteenth century, handed down to us by manuscript Français 1447 preserved at the Département des Manuscrits of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France.

And in it we find the following amazing piece of information.

The two main characters, the valiant knights Claris and Laris, arrive to an enchanted place, which features a number of aspects we already know well from the legendary tales concerning the magical abode of the Apennine Sibyl:

«Through a gate they went; - In the most charming town they entered, - such they had never seen before the like; [...] - I believe this is a Devil's artifact, - Witchcraft or enchantment».

[In the original Old French text: «Atant une porte passerent, - En la plus bele vile entrerent, - Qu'onques mes eussent veue; [...] - Je croi, que ce soit deablie, - Feerie ou enchantement»].

The two knights enter into a magical realm, a product of wizardry, in which the streets were adorned «with rich silken draperies - And precious kingly fabrics; - With so much gold and silver» («De riches pailles de cendax - Et d'osterins emperiax; - Tant i avoit or et argent»). And they are welcomed by handsome damsels, and they attend a luscious banquet, and take rest in a magnificent chamber.

But the lavish lures just conceal a deadly trap, which is ensnaring Claris and Laris:

«And now that you have come here,
You will be held in great honor;
In this place you will be with us
All the days of your life.
We are all at your service,
If you do not complain of that,
For in accord with your wishes,
You will get everything you may ask for
And think of for your own pleasure,
So much so that you will never be able to leave
This abode».

[In the original Old French text:
«Et puis que ci estez venuz,
A grant hennor serez tenuz;
Ceanz nos ferez compaignie
Tretouz les jours de vostre vie.
Toutes sommes a vo vouloir,
Si ne vous en doit pas doloir,
Car a vostre vouloir avrez
Tout ce, que demander savrez
Et pourpenser a grant loisir,
Fors tant, que ne porrez issir
Ja mes de ceste enfermerie»].

Who is the ruler of such a perilous, enchanted place? Who presides over such a magical kingdom, which attracts knights and noblemen by presenting them with beautiful fairies and glittering riches and appealing food? Who is the queen of a place that, once you are allowed in, you are never permitted to leave for the rest of your life, imprisoned in a neverending revelry?

Fig. 35 - The excerpt from *Claris et Laris* that depicts an enchanted place in which knights are retained forever (manuscript Français 1447, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 90r)

Is she a Sibyl of the Apennines? The answer is no.

Let's see in the following lines who she is:

«She replied to him [Laris] that her name was Morgan, sister to King Arthur, and she was a fay».

[In the original Old French text:

«Li dist, que Morgans iert nonmee,

La suer Artus, et estoit fee»].

So, in the thirteenth century, long before *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* were written, a fairy queen is already ruling an enchanted realm, marked by specific traits we will later find attached to a magical place hidden within a Mount Sibyl's cave, a later abode presided over by an Apennine Sibyl.

Fig. 36 - Morgan le Fay as the ruler of the enchanted abode (manuscript Français 1447, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, folium 90r)

The interesting thing is that the fairy queen is not the Apennine Sibyl, but Morgan le Fay. A legendary character which fully belongs to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian literary cycle.

Just a mere chance? Just an insignificant coincidence which links two utterly different legendary tales, the Apennine Sibyl's and King Arthur's, both ultimately rooted in a same kind of well-known, widespread chivalric literary genre and simply making use of the same trivial narrative schemes?

Perhaps. Yet perhaps not.

Because if we deepen our search, we stumble upon another astounding coincidence, even more remarkable than that retrieved in *Claris et Laris*.

We are now about to visit a mountain. In Italy. And make acquaintance with another enchanted realm. Once again, our host will not be a Sibyl either.

Incredibly enough, it will be, once more, Morgan le Fay.

10. A fay from Britain to the land of Italy

We are now about to meet fairy queens and subterranean realms, in the land of Italy: however, the realm we are going to meet is not the Apennine Sibyl's.

Could this peculiar element, connected to magical abodes situated in very special mountains, be a further foreign narrative layer concealing the true nature of the legend which concerns a Sibyl of the Apennines? Is this a further, crucial step we are about to make in the delicate process of taking out the concentric narrative leaves which hide the pulsating nucleus of the myth that lives in the Sibillini Mountain Range, in the Italian Apennines?

Let's see and find out.

One of the most antique examples, and almost unknown, of a narrative scheme concerning a magical realm set in Italy is present in a substantially neglected manuscript originally preserved at Newbattle Abbey, a benedictine monastery not far from Edinburgh, Scotland. The manuscript contains *Floriant et Florète*, a minor chivalric romance written in Old French and dating to the second half of the thirteenth century. The manuscript, including sixty-nine leaves, was discovered in the abbey's library in the second half of the nineteenth century and published in 1873, and is currently preserved at the New York Public Library (manuscript De Ricci, no. 122). Further fifteenth-century manuscripted versions of this romance exist at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France (Département des Manuscrits, Français 1492 and 1493), with the title *Le Roment de Floriant et de Flourete*, but the Scottish manuscript is more antique and it is the only text presenting the form of a metrical poem.

becomes a valiant knight. When Floriant comes to know his kingly lineage, King Arthur and all the knights of the Round Table pledge to help him: they promise to win Sicily back for him against the usurper Maragoz. Arthur sets sails to Sicily, he and his knights fight the usurper and his ally, the Emperor of Constantinople, at Monreale and Palermo, two Sicilian towns, and then Floriant is restored to power.

Scholars (Megan Moore, 2014) have seen in this antique poem an effort to establish a bridge between the Matter of Britain and the Mediterranean region, with the author staging a war being waged by King Arthur against the rulers of Byzantium, and portraying in the poem Sicilian merchants from Palermo who come to and fro Britain to exchange all sorts of goods («marcheant sunt arrivez - Qui de Palerne furet né. - Droit de Bretagne revenoient - Dras et merchandise apportoient», Folium 24r).

Amid all that, there is one specific element we want to stress: incredibly enough, this romance stages an Italian mountain, a fairy queen, and a realm in which no one can ever die.

Is that queen the Apennine Sibyl? No: she is «Morgain», or Morgan le Fay, the most famous half-sister to King Arthur; and the Italian mount is Mongibel, the ancient name for Mount Etna, the volcano sitting in the vicinity of the town of Catania, Sicily.

«Three fairies coming from the see - Their master is called - Morgan, King Arthur's sister [...] - Morgan, with no further delay, - seized the child [Floriant], and then took their way back, - towards Mongibel they headed - where their castle lay [...] - They had the child well nourished and tended».

[In the original Old French text: «Trois fées de la mer salée - La mestresse d'aux ert nommée - Morgain, la suer le roi Artu [...] - Morgain, sans plus de demorée, - L'a pris. Aitant s'en tornernet, - Vers Mongibel s'acheminèrent - Quar c'estoit lor mestre chastel [...] - Bien le font norrir et garder», Folium 5v].

At the Mongibel, or Mount Etna, Floriant undergoes «training in all arts» («Morgan [...] par nuit m'embla, - Droit à Mongibel m'emporta, - Bien me fist norrir et garder - Et de tous les ars doctrinner», Folium 30v). When he grows up, Floriant asks Morgan about his true lineage:

«One day Floriant came to Morgan - and so he spoke to her: - “Dame, he said, listen to my words. - I know well you are my mother, - yet I do not know the name of my father.” - When Morgan heard his words, [... she said] “And do you know which direction you will head now? - You are to go to King Arthur, and you will tell him - That Morgan, his sister, salutes him».

[In the original Old French text: «Un jor est à Morgain venu - Florians, si li demanda: - "Dame, fet-il, entendez çà. - Bien croi que vous estes ma mere, - Mais je ne connois pas mon pere." - Quant Morgain l'ot ansi parler, [... fet-ele] "Et savez quel part vous irois? - Au roi Arti, si li dirois - Que Morgain, sa soeur, le salue», Folia 7r and 7v].

Mongibel, the magical castle of the mountain, is a place where no one can ever pass away. Here is how Morgan describes it to Floriant, who at the end of the romance is nearing death (Folium 69v):

«My friend, you are about to die
And leave this life,
Nothing can help you,
No medicine can save you:
That is why I wanted to have you here.
Know then, by your own eyes and with no lies
That this castle of Mongibel is enchanted;
Know that the truth is as follows:
No one can ever die here.
King Arthur, when he will be on the verge of death,
Will be brought here by my brothers;
When he will be about to die,
You must know that I will bring him here».

[In the original Old French text:
«Amis, vous deviez mourir
Et de cest siecle departir,
Nus ne vous i péust aidier,
Mecine n'i éust mestier:
Por itant vous fis ci venir.
Sachiès de voir et sanza mentir

Que cist chastuaus [Mongibel] si est feez;
 Sachiez que ço est veritez:
 Nus hons ne puet caienz mori.
 Li rois Artus, au defenir,
 Mes freres, i ert amenez;
 Quant il sera à mort navrez,
 Sachiez que je l'i amenrai».

Fig. 38 - The final folium of *Floriant et Florète* with the passage on King Arthur and the Mongibel (folium 69v, manuscript De Ricci, no. 122, NewYork Public Library)

The manuscript ends a few lines after the listed words. However, we know the closing of *Floriant et Florète* by virtue of the fifteenth-century manuscripts available at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France: both Floriant and Florète enter the Mongibel to live an eternal life, and «after that, nobody was who ever heard of them anymore» («Et oncques puis ne fut nul qui ouist parler d'eulx»).

Unbelievable as it might seem, we must remember that *Floriant et Florète* is not the only antique text which establishes a peculiar connection between King Arthur and Mount Etna as his final resting place.

Fig. 39 - A vision of Mount Etna in our present time

According to a most ancient tradition, Arthur is still living an eternal life in the enchanted island of Avalon in Britain, but a few medieval authors reports a truly different location: Mongibel in Sicily was mentioned by Gervase of Tilbury in his *Otia Imperialia*, written at the beginning of the thirteenth century; the same did Caesarius of Heisterbach with his *Dialogus Miraculorum* dating to near 1220; and a mention is also found in Stephen of Bourbon's *Tractatus de diversis materiis predicabilibus*, written in the first half of the thirteenth century. All of them set the immortal King Arthur beneath Mount Etna, a conspicuous evidence of the migration of tales belonging to the Matter of Britain from northern Europe to Italy and back

again, mainly owing to the ceaseless wandering of oral performers and storytellers who used to tread all the roads of the continent. But the listed authors do not provide further details on the magical abode hidden within the Sicilian volcano.

As to *Floriant et Florète*, the striking fact is that, some one hundred fifty years before *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* were written, a chivalric poem was already narrating of a fairy lady, who lived in a very special mountain - a volcano - set in Italy and whose abode was an enchanted place, bestowed of the gift of immortality. Furthermore, like in the legend of 'Tannhäuser', dating to the same period as *Guerrino* and *The Paradise*, a main character of the story vanishes forever within the fairy realm and is to be seen no more in our world.

And the fairy lady is not the Apennine Sibyl at all: instead, she is Morgan le Fay, a prominent figure belonging to the Arthurian cycle.

The Apennine Sibyl and Morgan le Fay: what sort of relationship does exist between the two, if any?

In the next paper, we will see that a connection does actually exist. And that link is so strong that we might even suspect that the two ladies have much in common.

Much more than we can ever expect.

11. An oracle and magician whose name is Morgan le Fay

In our previous articles, we have seen that a medieval literary poem, *Floriant et Florète*, dating to the thirteenth century, stages a magical lady, bestowed with wizardly powers, living in a magical palace set within a very special mountain, situated in Italy.

However, this lady is not the Apennine Sibyl, and the mountain is not a peak of the Apennines. As a matter of fact, the Apennine Sibyl will come on to the scene at the beginning of the fifteenth century only, preceded by a

similar necromantic queen depicted in the French poem *Huon d'Auvergne* and in Andrea da Barberino's romance *Ugone d'Avernia*.

Who is the lady who seems to partake of a number of significant features which belong, as we were accustomed to considering, to the Sibyl of the Apennines?

The poem *Floriant et Florète* points to a specific, unexpected direction: that lady is Morgan le Fay, and it seems that she too was used to live in hidden or underground places, such as Mount Etna, the great Italian volcano.

And there is also another poem, written in the thirteenth century as well, *Claris et Laris*, which stages an enchanted realm, featuring many traits in common with the Apennine Sibyl's magical abode, but ruled by a different queen, yet one we know already: again, Morgan, King Arthur's half-sister.

But who is Morgan le Fay?

In this paper, we dare not confront with this towering figure fully belonging to the Arthurian cycle: throughout the centuries, she has been the subject of extensive, ceaseless research in the domains of literature, mythography, history, and psychology, and it falls outside the scope of the present work to discuss in detail the origin, traits and meaning of this mighty fairy character, a leading protagonist of the Matter of Britain's legendary tradition and lore.

The most renowned description of the character of Morgan le Fay is contained in the world-famous book *Le Morte d'Arthur* by Thomas Malory, first published in London in 1485: according to Malory, she is the evil half-sister to King Arthur, a sorceress who is determined to pursue the ruin of his relative out of a relentless resentment. A wicked figure, a villain, and an experienced necromancer.

Nonetheless, this is only the final outcome of a long process through which Morgan's character has undergone a significant transformation, starting from a most remarkable beginning.

Because the earliest known written mention concerning Morgan is reported by Geoffrey of Monmouth in his *Vita Merlini* (*The Life of Merlin*), written around 1150 and available today in its entirety in one manuscript only (Cotton MS Vespasian E IV, folia 112v–138v), preserved at the British Library in London. In his work, Geoffrey narrates of a special, enchanted island:

«The Island of Fruits, which men call 'The Blessed Isle' gets its name from the fact that it produces all things of itself; the fields there have no need of the ploughs of the farmers and all cultivation is lacking except what nature provides: of its own accord it produces grain and grapes, and fruit trees grow in its woods from the close-clipped grass. The ground of its own accord produces everything instead of merely grass, and people live there a hundred years or more».

[In the original Latin text: «Insula Pomorum qua Fortunata vocatur, Ex re nomen habet, quia per se singula profert: Non opus est illi sulcantibus arva colonis; Omnis abest cultus nisi quem natura ministrat: Ultra foecundas segetes producit et uvas, Nataque poma suis pretonso germine silvis; Omnia gignit humus vice graminis ultro redundans. Annis centenis aut ultra vivitur illic»].

According to Geoffrey of Monmouth, in this heavenly island nine fairy sisters live, whose the handsomest is Morgen, endowed with wisdom, healing knowledge and magical powers:

«There nine sisters rule by a pleasing set of laws those who come to them from our country. She who is first of them is more skilled in the healing art, and excels her sisters in the beauty of her person, Morgen is her name, and she has learned what useful properties all the herbs contain, so that she can cure sick bodies. She also knows an art by which to change her shape, and to cleave the air on new wings like Daedalus; when she wishes she is at Brest, Chartres, or Pavia, and when she will she slips down from the air onto our shores.

And men say that she has taught mathematics to her sisters».

[In the original Latin text:

«Illic jura novem geniali lege sorores
 Dant his qui veniunt nostris ex partibus ad se:
 Quarum que prior est fit doctior arte medendi;
 Exceditque suas forma prestante sorores;
 Morgen ei nomen, didicitque quid utilitatis
 Gramina cuncta ferant, ut languida corpora curet;
 Ars quoque nota sibi qua scit mutare figuram,
 Et resecare novis quasi Dædalus aera pennis;
 Cum vult est Bristi, Carnoti, sive Papie,
 Cum vult in nostris ex aere labitur horis.
 Hancque mathematicam dicunt didicisse sorores»].

Insula Pomorum quæ Fortunata vocatur,
 Ex re nomen habet, quia per se singula profert:
 Non opus est illi sulcantibus arva colonis;
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 Ultro fæcundas segetes producit et uvas,
 Nataque poma suis prætonso germine silvis;
 Omnia gignit humus vice graminis ultro redundans.
 Annis centenis aut ultra vivitur illic,
 Illic jura novem geniali lege sorores
 Dant his qui veniunt nostris ex partibus ad se:
 Quarum quæ prior est fit doctior arte medendi;
 Exceditque suas forma præstante sorores;
 Morgen ei nomen, didicitque quid utilitatis

Gramina cuncta ferant, ut languida corpora curet;
 Ars quoque nota sibi qua scit mutare figuram,
 Et resecare novis quasi Dædalus aera pennis;
 Cum vult est Bristi, Carnoti, sive Papie,
 Cum vult in nostris ex aere labitur horis.
 Hancque mathematicam dicunt didicisse sorores,

Et nos quo decuit Morgen suscepit honore,
 Inque suis talamis posuit super aurea regem
 Stulta², manuque sibi detexit vulnus honesta,
 Inspexitque diu; tandemque redire salutem
 Posse sibi dixit, si secum tempore longo
 Esset, et ipsius vellet medicamine fungi.
 Gaudentes igitur regem commisimus illi,
 Et dedimus ventis redeundo vela secundis. *

Fig. 40 - Geoffrey of Monmouth's *Vita Merlini* from the transcript published in Paris in 1837

Thus, according to this most antique description, Morgen lives in an enchanted island teeming with all kinds of fruits. The most beautiful amid

nine women, she is a healer and a fay, owing to her ability to change her own shape and fly.

In the magical island, continues Geoffrey of Monmouth, Morgen received the wounded King Arthur in a rich palace, and asked him to stay with her for an endless time to have his wounds healed:

«[...] With the prince we came there,
and Morgen received us with fitting honour,
and in her chambers she placed the king on a golden bed
[...] at length she said that health could be restored
to him if he stayed with her for a long time
and made use of her healing art».

[In the original Latin text:

«[...] cum principe venimus illuc,
Et nos quo decuit Morgen suscepit honore,
Inque suis talamis posuit super aurea regem
[...] tandemque redire salutem
Posse sibi dixit, si secum tempore longo
Esset, et ipsius vellet medicamine fungi»].

An isolated, enchanted abode, inhabited by a fairy lady, a place where to take rest forever. And the island, as Geoffrey of Monmouth himself says in another work, the *Historia Regum Britanniae* (*The History of the Kings of Britain*, Book XI, Chapter II, following the text taken from folium 53v of manuscript Latin 6040 preserved at the Département des Manuscrits of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France, dating to the end of the twelfth century), is the mythical isle of Avalon:

«[...] Even the renowned King Arthur himself was wounded deadly, and was borne thence unto the island of Avalon for the healing of his wounds».

[In the original Latin text: «Sed et inclytus ille Arturus rex letaliter vulneratus est, qui illinc ad sananda vulnera sua in insulam Avallonis evectus»].

But, according to scholars, Geoffrey of Monmouth's description comes from a much older excerpt, coming straight from the first century and the

Roman age. The nine sisters depicted by the medieval writer seem to be drawn straight from *De Situ Orbis*, a work written by Latin author Pomponius Mela, an ancient Roman geographer.

Fig. 41 - The excerpt on King Arthur and Avalon from the *Historia Regum Britanniae* (folium 53v, manuscript Latin 6040, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France)

In this ancient work, Pomponius Mela portrays a special island (which scholars identify as today's Île de Sein, an island off the coast of Brittany, France), as shown in the text drawn from a precious edition printed in Paris in 1507:

«In the Britannic Sea, opposite the coast of the Ossismi, the isle of Sena [Sein] belongs to a Gallic divinity and is famous for its oracle, whose priestesses, sanctified by their perpetual virginity, are reportedly nine in number. They call the priestesses Gallizenae and think that because they

have been endowed with unique powers, they stir up the seas and the winds by their magic charms, that they turn into whatever animals they want, that they cure what is incurable among other peoples, that they know and predict the future, but that it is not revealed except to sea-voyagers and then only to those traveling to consult them».

[In the original Latin text: «Sena in Britannico mari Ossismicis aduersa litoribus, Gallici numinis oraculo insignis est, cuius antistites perpetua virginitate sanctae numero novem esse traduntur: Gallicenas vocant, putantque ingeniis singularibus praeditas maria ac ventos concitare carminibus, seque in quae velint animalia vertere, sanare quae apud alios insanabilia sunt, scire ventura et praedicare, sed non nisi deditas navigantibus, et in id tantum ut se consulerent profectis»].

Fig. 42 - The passage on the nine prophetesses from Pomponius Mela's *De Situ Orbis*, as it appears in an edition printed in Paris in 1507

So Morgan le Fay - who in medieval times we have found as a resident fay in enchanted towns and Italian volcanoes - at the very origin of her myth

was connected to an enchanted or specially blessed place, and presented the characters of a prophetess with oracular powers, a priestess, a healer, and a magician, who could fly, transform herself, and command the seas and the winds by her spells. She lived in a magical abode, in which a mighty knight and king was asked to stay forever.

All such features were mixed and intertwined in the most antique semblance of this northern-European fairy. Features that are not alien indeed to the later prophetess whose origin we are currently investigating, the Apennine Sibyl.

It is manifest that some kind of tenuous link seems to exist between Morgan le Fay and the Sibyl of the Apennines: a few basic traits they share in common, some overlapping in their roles as rulers of enchanted abodes, and a hint that very special mountains might be of relevance to both.

Yet, this is only the beginning. The more we proceed into our search, the more the connection between the two will appear to grow larger and steadier.

Because there is one astounding turning point.

A turning point that has been overlooked for centuries and centuries. An element which connects strongly and indelibly Morgan le Fay to the world of the Sibyls. A relationship which is established between them in a minor chivalric poem, written by a secondary poet, in a country which is neither Britain, nor France, the two homelands of the Matter of Britain.

This relationship has never been highlighted adequately before the issue of the present paper. Thus what we are about to present is an absolute cornerstone in the study of the Apennine Sibyl's legend and lore: the point of passage between Morgan le Fay and the Sibyls, with a specific significance for what was due to become the still-to-be Sibyl of the Apennines.

Let's see together what we are talking about.

12. *The Sibyls and Famurgan, master of arcane arts*

It is the year 1185 and, according to scholars, a knight and poet from Germany, Hartmann von Aue, writes a rhymed poem, whose title is *Erec*, an adaptation from the much more popular work *Erec et Enide* by Chrétien de Troyes.

Hartmann von Aue was not to become the most famous German writer of his age: twenty years later, Wolfram von Eschenbach, subsequently recognized as one of the most influential authors in medieval literature, would write his *Parzival*, probably the greatest German epic ever written; and Gottfried von Strassburg was about to write *Tristan*, another cornerstone in the wondrous scenario of the Matter of Britain. In France, Chrétien de Troyes was adding to the Arthurian Cycle with such masterpieces as *Yvain* and *Lancelot*.

However, Hartmann von Aue will be the one to provide today's scholars with a most amazing proof of the literary connection which links Morgan le Fay and the Sibyls, with specific reference to the traits which will be peculiar to the Apennine Sibyl.

A proof that has almost been ignored for centuries by everybody, an evidence which explains many subsequent literary facts, and which we are now going to present to the widest audience of scholars and researchers.

We must remember that, during the twelfth century, Morgan had been retaining her original traits as a wise savant, a remarkable feature which is also shared with the later Sibyl of the Apennines. In one of the earliest romances belonging to the Arthurian cycle, Chrétien de Troyes' *Yvain ou le Chevalier au Lion* (*Yvain, the Knight of the Lion*), written in 1180, Morgan appears as «the Wise» («Morge la sage»), with reference to her healing skills: a title also enjoyed by the Apennine Sibyl, whom Andrea da Barberino calls «wise» and «most learned» («savia Sibilla» and «sapiantissima Sibilla») in his *Guerrino the Wretch*.

But a change was about to take place. At the end of that same twelfth century, Hartmann von Aue writes *Erec*". And, in it, we find something truly amazing and unexpected. And thoroughly overlooked.

Fig. 43 - Mogan the wise from Chrétien de Troyes' *Yvain ou le Chevalier au Lion* (folium 216r, manuscript Français 1450, Département des Manuscrits, Bibliothèque Nationale de France) and the same attribute ascribed to the Apennine Sibyl in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapters CXXXVIII and CXLV and from the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

The single existing complete copy of *Erec* is preserved in Wien, at the Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, the Austrian National Library, in the Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663: it is the most famous manuscript called *Ambraser Heldenbuch*, a sixteenth-century work containing a collection of twenty-five old-German epic narratives all dating to the twelfth and thirteenth century.

The Folium 40v contains the twelfth-century clue which changes our perception of the evolution of the legendary tale concerning a Sibyl of the Apennines.

Fig. 44 - The opening miniature of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 (*Ambraser Heldenbuch*), preserved at the Österreichische Nationalbibliothek in Wien

In this episode, Erec is wounded, and Queen Guinevere takes care of him at King Arthur's court. She has a magical ointment, a special medicament which heals all wounds and abates all pain. It was given to her by Morgan le Fay, whom we already know as a skilled healer according to the most antique tradition we mentioned in a preceding article:

«If any man wonders, and would gladly know where this ointment came from, it was left long ago by Morgan le Fay, the King's sister, when she died».

[In the original Old German text: «wundert nu dhainen man - der es gerne vernéme - von wannen ditz phlafter kime - das hette Famurgan - des kuniges schwefter da verlan - lanng daruor da fy erftarb»].

Fig. 45 - Folium 40v from the *Ambraser Heldenbuch* with the passage on Famurgan and her magical ointment from Hartmann von Aue's *Erec*

In Hartmann von Aue's work, initially Morgan le Fay, «Famurgan», is presented as the same benign healer we already know from the antique tradition reported by Geoffrey of Monmouth, ultimately to be ascribed to Latin author Pomponius Mela. And Morgan's magical traits too, as described by von Aue, are similar to those we found in Geoffrey of Monmouth's *Vita Merlini*, with the addition that now Morgan is turned into a fully divine being:

«What great power and arcane arts perished with her! She was a goddess. Her wonders cannot be told, we must be silent about them, those wonders that that same woman performed. But as far as I can, I will tell you more. When she manifested her magic arts, she could travel with great speed around the world and quickly come back. I don't know who taught this to

her. Before you could turn your hand or wink, she could leave and reappear just as quickly. She lived just as she wished; in the air or on earth - if she wanted she could sleep on the waves or live underwater. It wasn't difficult for her, she could just as easily live in fire or dew; the lady knew how to do that. And if she wanted, she could turn someone into a bird or animal. After that she could quickly give him his usual shape. She knew all sorts of magic arts».

[In the original Old German text: «was stacher lifte an jr verdarb - von frembden fynnen - sÿ was ein gottinen - Man mag die wunder nit gesagen - von Ir man mus jr mer verdagen - der die selb fraw phlag - doch so ich maiste mag - so sag ich was sÿ kunde - wenn sÿ begunde - augen jr zauberlist - so het sÿ in kurtzer frist - die welt vmbfarn da - vnd kam wider sa - ich wayßs nit wer sÿ es lerte - ee ich die vmbkerte - oder zugeschluege die pra - so fuer sÿ hin vnd schin doch fa - sÿ lebete ir vil werde - im luffte als auf der erde - mochte sÿ zu rue schweben - auf dem wage vnd darundter leben - auch was jr das vnteure - sÿ wonnet in dem fewre - also sanfft als auf dem tawe - ditz kunde die fraue - vnd so sÿ des began - so mochte sÿ den man - Ze vogel oder ze tiere - darnach gab sÿ im schiere - wider sein geschafft - sÿ kunde doch zaubers die kraft»].

Fig. 46 - The excerpt on the magical powers of Famurgan from Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* (Folium 40v of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 *Ambraser Heldenbuch*)

So Morgan le Fay is portrayed as a mighty, experienced wizard, who knew well the craft of magical arts («fÿ kunde doch zaubers die kraft»)

But now the time of «Famurgan» as a mere benign healer is over. And, for the first time, evil sorcery and necromancy make their dark appearance.

Gloomy traits that Hartmann von Aue, at the end of the twelfth century, openly associates with specific characters belonging to a most ancient tradition, lost in classical antiquity.

He states a forthright, unambiguous association between Morgan le Fay and the Sibyls. As we will see in the next article.

13. A bond of necromancy established between Morgan le Fay and the Sibyls

We are perusing Folium 40v of the Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663, also called *Ambraser Heldenbuch*, a manuscript which contains the only integral version of Hartmann von Aue's twelfth-century poem *Erec*. The vellum pages include an excerpt on «Famurgan», or Morgan le Fay, in which King Arthur's half-sister is depicted and praised as a skilled healer and a most powerful wizard, proficient in magical arts.

But as we proceed further with the reading, the description takes an utterly different turn. And here is how Hartmann von Aue presents the new, sinister traits of Morgan le Fay:

«She lived much against God: for under her command were the birds of the wild, of forests and fields, and what is most important to me, the evil spirits, which are called demons, were all under her control. She could work wonders, for even the dragons of the air and the fish of the sea brought tribute to her».

[In the original Old German text: «sÿ lebete vaft wider got - wann es wartette jr gepot - das gefugl zu dem wilde - on walde vnd on geulde - vnd daz mich daz maifte - die vbeln geifte - die da tiefln sint genant - die waren alle vnnder jr handt - fÿ mochte wunder machen - wann jr muften die

trachen - von den lufften bringen - stewre zu jrn dingen - die Vifche von dem wage»].

Fig. 47 - The passage on Morgan's evil nature from Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* (Folium 40v of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 *Ambraser Heldenbuch*)

And there is more to that. Hartmann von Aue is now ready to stage Morgan le Fay's final transformation into a full demon, a being who partakes of the nature of Hell and commands by a single gesture the gloomiest subterranean powers:

«She also had kin deep in Hell; the devil was her companion. He paid tribute to her, even from the flames, however much she wanted. And whatever she wanted from the earthly realm, that she took enough of without any bother. The earth would grow no plants, if her power were not manifested, as I move my hand».

[In the original Old German text: «auch het sÿ mage - tieff in der helle - der teufl was jr gefelle - der fant jr steure - auch aus dem feure - wieuil sÿ des wolte - vnd was sÿ haben solte - von erdrtriche - des nam sÿ im angftliche -

alles selb genug - die erde dhain wurtzen trug - Ir ware jr crafft erkannt - als mir mein felbs hanndt»].

Fig. 48 - Morgan and the netherworld from Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* (Folium 40v of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 *Ambraser Heldenbuch*)

The description of Morgan le Fay we have been reading up to now, written by German writer Hartmann von Aue at the end of the twelfth century, might perfectly fit the main character and traits of the Apennine Sibyl as she will appear before our eyes more than two centuries later in the works by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale: a woman who is a sort of goddess, a fiendish being, in close contact with the Netherworld, who can cast spells to create illusions and induce transformations of men and animals (here we still miss the Sibyl's sensual aspects, but they are soon to come, too, in later literary portraits of Morgan, as we will see in subsequent articles).

However, in this excerpt we still lack a manifest, indisputable evidence of an actual link to Sibyls. Is there any?

Is Morgan le Fay, a chief character in the Arthurian cycle, closely and irrefutably connected to the lore of Sibyls, the prophesying oracles of the classical age?

Yes. This manifest, irrefutable evidence is provided by the same Hartmann von Aue, in the very lines that follow the ones we have already presented above.

Let's see how Hartmann von Aue proceeds with his description of Morgan le Fay:

«Since the Sybil died, and Ericto perished, of which Lucanus tells us, and sorcery which they could command had died away ages ago, with her it all came back (about which I don't want to say much at this time, since it would take too long). Since then, the earthly realm probably has had no better mistress of the magic arts than Morgan le Fay, of whom I have already spoken. He couldn't be a wiser man, whoever wished to take away great suffering, that she could mix up a plaster for him. Yes, I ween that if a man looked everywhere he could not, however busily he searched out powers from books of magic, find such powerful arts that she practiced against Christ».

[In the original Old German text: «Seyt daz sibilla erstarb - vnd Ericto verdarb - von der vns Lucanuf zalt - daz jr zauberlich gewalt - wem fy wolte gepot - der dauor was lanng todt - daz er erstund wol gefunt - von der ich euch hie zestund - nu nicht mer fagen wil - wann es wurde ze vil - sy gewan das erdtrich - das wisset warlich - von zauberlichen fynne - nie besser maisterynne - dann Famurgan - von der ich euch gefaget han - wann da were er nicht weyfer man - wer im wolte daran - nemen gros lafter - auch fey ein phlafter - fur jn gebruefen kunde - Ja wann man nyndert funde - wie fere man fy wolte erfuchen - die crafft aus Artztpuchen - so krefftigkliche lifte - die fy wider crifte»].

Here is the connection, the missing link between the Matter of Britain, featuring the healer and wizard Morgan le Fay, and the lore of classical Sibyls. It is right here that Hartmann von Aue, in the year 1185, establishes a specific connection between King Arthur's half-sister and the Sibyls belonging to an ancient Roman-Greek, mediterranean tradition.

Fig. 49 - Morgan, the Sibyl and Ericho from Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* (Folium 40v of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 *Ambraser Heldenbuch*)

And the link is based on magic power, and the acquaintance with the Devil and with the evil subterranean powers. And, in addition to that, on necromancy.

Because the Sibyls of the classical world, together with Morgan le Fay, are now included in a same party in which a main role is also played by

Erictho, the impious Greek witch who used to perform necromantic rituals on human corpses. One of the most repugnant characters of antique literature, a ghastly sorcerer, depicted by first-century Latin author Marcus Annaeus Lucanus in his “Pharsalia” (Book VI): a mighty necromancer, with a horrifying semblance, who could raise the dead to a new abominable life and draw oracular responses right from their corrupted bodies.

Lucanus' Erictho, like Hartmann von Aue's Morgan le Fay, is a companion to the dark powers: according to Lucanus, she is «dear to the deities of the Netherworld» («grata deis Erebis»), she knows «the abodes of Hell and the mysteries of subterranean Pluto» («domos Stygias arcanaque Ditis»), and she «addresses no prayer to Heaven, invokes no divine aid with suppliant hymn» («nec superos orat nec cantu supplice numen auxiliare vocat»).

In this gloomy, necromantic framework, which Sibyl is Hartmann von Aue specifically referring to? He doesn't tell. But our mind immediately runs to one of the most renowned Sibyls: the Cumaean Sibyl, and her ancestor the Cimmerian Sibyl, both residing in the Italian town of Cumae.

It is the Cumaean Sibyl who is celebrated by Publius Vergilius Maro in Book VI of his “Aeneid” as a guide to Aeneas into the Otherworld. It is the Cumaean Sibyl who utters fateful prophecies, «terrific riddles she yells, as she sings in her cave, the truth enshrouded in darkness» («Cumaea Sibylla - horrendas canit ambages antroque remugit - obscuris vera involvens»). It is the Cumaean Sibyl who lives in her «ghastly, secret recesses, the huge cavern of the Sibyl» («horrendaque procul secreta Sibyllae antrum immane»). Again, it is the Cumaean Sibyl who commands Aeneas to make an offering to Hecate, the Greek goddess associated to witchcraft and necromancy, with the hero from Troy «appealing to Hecate by his voice, calling to the heaven and to vast Erebus» («voce vocans Hecaten caeloque Ereboque potentem»). Finally, it is the Cimmerian oracle, according to Strabo, the Greek geographer and historian, a Sibyl, according to Sextus Aurelius Victor, who presided over the temple «where the dead uttered prophecies as if they were alive».

Morgan le Fay. A Sibyl, possibly the Cumaean. And a Greek witch, Erictho.

In the twelfth century, in a German-speaking literary environment, the three of them are considered as the most powerful magicians in the whole world.

And the three of them have to do with the Netherworld, and the evil entities that live in the gloomy darkness beneath. And they all have something to do with oracular responses, obtained through a most impious and forbidden craft: necromancy, the art of dealing with the dead to obtain prophecies for the living.

Fig. 50 - An enlarged view of the word «Sibilla» which appears in Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* (Folium 40v of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 *Ambraser Heldenbuch*)

But what has it all got to do with our posterior, fifteenth-century Apennine Sibyl?

The way to the fifteenth century is still long. Here, we are still considering a minor chivalric poem, “*Erec*”, written by a minor German poet, Hartmann von Aue, more than two hundred years before the literary appearance of the Apennine Sibyl amid the lofty peaks of the Italian Apennines.

Yet, as we will see in the next articles, the road of myth will direct its own course in that precise direction.

Further clues, retrieved in the two subsequent centuries, will show that Morgan le Fay, a powerful witch, an antique oracle, living in an enchanted isolated place, in close contact with the gloomiest subterranean powers, will accentuate her kinship with the Sibyls, and with a specific kind of Sibyl.

By this process, a process we will retrace in the next articles, she will be getting nearer and nearer to her final destination: a Sibyl of the Apennines.

END OF PART 1

**Please refer to Part 2
for the continuation of the research paper**